

UP2030

Urban Planning and design ready for 2030

D6.7 – Neutrality Story Maps for the Pilot Cities 2

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This project has received funding from the Horizon Innovation Actions under the grant agreement n° 101096405.

SCAN QR CODE

About UP2030:

UP2030 is dedicated to aiding cities in achieving climate neutrality through enhanced urban planning and design. The project introduces the innovative 5UP approach to support city stakeholders and local authorities in integrating climate-neutral strategies into their everyday actions and long-term planning. Focused on promoting spatial justice and inclusive participation, UP2030 empowers communities and local governments to become agents of change, driving socio-technical transitions that enhance urban liveability and sustainability. The project's strategy aims to produce actionable insights and scalable solutions for urban environments, prioritizing resilience, equity, and sustainable urban development.

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Document Information

Grant Agreement Number	101096405	Acronym	UP2030	
Full Title	Urban Planning and Design ready for 2030			
Start Date	01/01/2023	Duration	36 months	
Project Website	https://up2030-he.eu/			
Deliverable	D6.7 – Neutrality Story Maps for Pilot Cities 2			
Work Package	WP6 – UP-TAKING – Dissemination, Exploitation, Communication and Sustainability of UP2030			
Date of Delivery	Contractual	31/12/2025	Actual	10/12/2025
Nature	DEC – Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.		Dissemination Level	PU-Public
Lead Beneficiary	VUB			
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Abstract	<p>Deliverable 6.7 documents the second co-design and development phase of the Neutrality Story Maps (NSM) platform, a key performance indicator of the UP2030 project. Building on the initial co-design efforts, this phase focused on developing and refining the platform through participatory methods, enhancing usability, and tailoring content to city-specific contexts. NSM serves as a digital storytelling tool that bridges communication between citizens and policymakers around climate neutrality, enabling multimedia, map-based narratives that reflect local concerns, aspirations, and initiatives.</p> <p>The deliverable outlines the collaborative methodology used by VUB and CERTH to guide this design phase, including workshops, surveys, interviews, and continuous stakeholder engagement from M22 to M36. Pilot cities played a central role in content creation, prototype testing, and validation, with activities aligned to the project’s action and upscale phases. The second round also incorporated feedback from cities not involved in the first design phase, ensuring broader representation and inclusivity. The deliverable also describes how the tool evolved during this period from a basic prototype into its final, fully developed form.</p> <p>In addition to the NSM platform itself, key outcomes include the development of localized NSM prototypes, citizen personas, and validated story content designed to foster behavioral change and deepen engagement with climate initiatives. The public launch of the platform marked a major milestone, supported by ongoing technical development and iterative feedback loops.</p>			

	Final analyses assessed storytelling outcomes across city groups, highlighting NSM’s potential to support climate-neutral urban transitions.
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Document History

Version	Issue Date	Stage	Description	Contributor
0.1	10/10/2025	Draft	Design of table of contents	VUB, CERTH
0.2	15/10/2025	Draft review	Review of table of content and executive summary	USTUTT, Fraunhofer
0.3	17/11/2025	Draft	First version of the deliverable	VUB, CERTH
0.4	19/11/2025	Draft review	Review of first draft	TU Delft
0.5	01/12/2025	Draft	Second version of the deliverable	VUB, CERTH
0.6	04/12/2025	Draft review	Coordination review	Fraunhofer
1.0	10/12/2025	Final	Final version ready for submission	VUB, CERTH

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Executive summary

Deliverable 6.7 (D6.7) builds on the first co-design phase of the Neutrality Story Maps (NSM) platform (see [D6.6 - Neutrality Story Maps for Pilot Cities 1](#)), presenting the results of the second round of development and detailing the collaborative process through which the platform was refined, populated with content, and prepared for public launch. As a key performance indicator (KPI) of the UP2030 project, NSM continued to evolve throughout this period, serving as a digital storytelling platform that bridges communication between citizens and policymakers.

NSM enables individuals to share personal stories, concerns, and aspirations related to climate and sustainability through multimedia, map-based narratives. At the same time, it allows cities to communicate climate data and pilot-specific initiatives in an accessible and engaging format. The second round of development focused on further developing and tailoring the tool to city-specific contexts, enhancing usability, and supporting behavior change by designing meaningful, localized story content.

This deliverable starts by outlining the methodology used to guide the second co-design round. The approach combined participatory design principles with iterative feedback loops, involving structured workshops, surveys, interviews, and continuous engagement with stakeholders. Data collection was embedded in the co-design and action phases, ensuring that both citizen and city perspectives informed the platform's evolution. Stakeholder engagement was central to the process, with pilot cities contributing to content creation, prototype testing, and validation. Analysis techniques included qualitative feedback synthesis and comparative review of story map drafts across city groups. The co-design activities for this round were streamlined with the timelines of the Action phase (M13-M26) and Upscale phase (M27-M36) of the project to minimize the effort required from the cities. These activities began with preparatory meetings, and included training sessions, structured feedback rounds, workshops, surveys, and continuous meetings with the pilot cities.

Between M19 and M21, Vrije Universiteit Brussel (VUB) and Centre for Research and Technology Hellas (CERTH) held preparatory meetings with each pilot city to reintroduce the NSM platform and co-define local implementation strategies. These meetings helped to further tailor the tool to city-specific needs, re-engage previous stakeholders, and onboard new participants, ensuring continuity and inclusivity in the second phase of co-design (see section 2.2.5 in [D6.6 - Neutrality Story Maps for Pilot Cities 1](#)).

The activities for the Action phase involved a training workshop at the General Assembly (GenA) held in Zagreb in M22, followed by in-depth one-on-one meetings and co-creation sessions with pilot cities, including the development of citizen personas in Belfast, and the creation of a working NSM prototype per city by M26.

The Upscale phase activities from M27 to M36 included three feedback workshops with pilot cities in M28 and M33, continuous meetings with pilot cities to refine their NSM prototype and a testing and validation session with students in M26, ensuring the platform's responsiveness and usability. The public launch in M34 marked a major milestone in the NSM lifecycle, supported by ongoing technical development from CERTH throughout this second round. The final NSMs were analyzed in two groups of cities to assess storytelling outcomes and their potential to foster behavior change and deepen engagement with climate neutrality initiatives.

The deliverable also describes how the initial user requirements collected during the first round of co-design evolved throughout the second round and the rest of this period. It further explains how the platform was developed iteratively, progressing from a basic first prototype to a complete, fully functional tool through several intermediate versions.

Finally, the deliverable reflects critically on the challenges of the co-design process, from resource constraints to uneven levels of engagement, and draws key lessons for future participatory platform

development. As NSMs are further embedded in the pilot cities' climate strategies, they represent a novel approach to inclusive urban governance and narrative-driven climate action.

Content alignment with other UP2030 deliverables

The UP2030 project fosters exchange and cooperation among partners and deliverables beyond the work packages (WPs) structure. Therefore, the content of this document has been developed in alignment with the work of Delft University of Technology (TU Delft), Universitat Internacional de Catalunya (UIC), Institute for Urban Excellence (iUE), Resilient Cities Network (RCities), and DRAXIS Environmental SA (DRAXIS) in WP3, WP4, WP5 and WP6. The following table lists the deliverables and milestones which provided input for this present document and future deliverables which could benefit from the content presented here.

Input from	Contributes to
D3.8 - Tools and approaches for inclusive participation and spatial justice 1 D6.6 - Neutrality Story Maps for Pilot Cities 1	D6.9 - Exploitation & Sustainability Planning Reports 2 D3.9 - Tools and approaches for promoting inclusive participation and spatial justice 2 D5.7 - Online Learning Programme materials
Mil.7 Cities establish user stories Mil.10 Cities run third workshop on action Mil.13 All cities have at least one successful prototype	Mil.15 Training programme successful delivery completed

The primary target groups for this document are the pilot cities and their liaison partners, particularly those involved in citizen engagement, digital storytelling, and climate communication. The main beneficiaries are cities seeking to enhance participatory climate action through narrative-driven tools, as well as partners contributing to the Massive Online Open Course (MOOC) and service platform. The insights presented in this document are also valuable for urban practitioners and cities beyond the project. Once finalized, the content will be distributed not only through the publication of the document but also via tutorial videos for the MOOC, city show-case events and outreach efforts, and promotion material disseminated through the VUB's, CERTH's and UP2030's communication channels.

Acronyms

Acronym	Full name
BoTu	Bospolder-Tussendijken
CERTH	Centre for Research and Technology Hellas
CIRCE	Centro de Investigación de Recursos y Consumos Energéticos
D	Deliverable
DRAXIS	DRAXIS Environmental SA
FAQs	Frequently Asked Questions
GenA	General Assembly
GIS	Geographic Information System
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
ICA	I-Catalist
ICLEI	ICLEI European Secretariat GMBH
iUE	Institute for Urban Excellence
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LAA	Learning Action Alliance
LIF	Law and Internet Foundation
M	Month
Mil	Milestone
MOOC	Massive Online Open Course
NSM	Neutrality Story Map
RCities	Resilient Cities Network
T	Task
TSPA	Thomas Stellmach Planning & Architecture
TU Delft	Delft University of Technology
UCAM	University of Cambridge

UI	User Interface
UIC	Universitat Internacional de Catalunya
UPV	Universitat Politecnica de Valencia
VUB	Vrije Universiteit Brussel
WP	Work Package

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and scope

This deliverable (D6.7) report is part of Work package 6 (WP6), Task 6.2 (T6.2) - Dissemination and communication actions. As part of T6.2, the Vrije Universiteit Brussel (VUB), in collaboration with its technical partner Centre for Research and Technology Hellas (CERTH), continues the development of the Neutrality Story Maps (NSM) platform for the UP2030 pilot cities.

Building on the foundations laid during the first round of co-design (M14-M18), this second round (M22-M36) deepens the co-creative process between VUB, CERTH, city representatives, and citizens. The aim is to refine and expand the digital storytelling methodology using maps, ensuring that the platform evolves in response to user feedback and emerging needs. To make the process more effective and minimize the effort and time management required from cities, the co-design activities were streamlined with the timelines and deadlines of the Action Phase and Upscale Phase of the project. This iterative approach strengthens tool ownership in each pilot city and contributes to the creation of a website platform that supports cities in engaging citizens in local climate neutrality actions. The cities' own engagement strategy will be complemented by the UP2030 web-based platform.

The digital storytelling methodology for NSM, developed entirely within UP2030, remains a key component of the toolkit for behavioral change and in-depth engagement, supporting inclusive planning and design practices. It continues to be developed and tested under T3.4 - Tools and Approaches for Promoting Inclusive Participation and Spatial Justice.

This document outlines the activities and findings from the second round of user and data requirement collection, conducted by VUB and CERTH. These insights inform the ongoing development of NSM and reflect the evolving perspectives, preferences, and values of diverse users.

1.2 Document structure

The document is organized as follows:

- ❖ Section 1 - Introduction: Provides an overview of the purpose and scope of the deliverable, situating within the broader UP2030 project. It outlines the structure of the document and introduces the key themes addressed in the second round of co-design.
- ❖ Section 2 - Methodology: Describes the methodological framework guiding the second round of co-design activities. It details the participatory approaches employed, the stakeholder groups involved, and the rationale behind the design choices.
- ❖ Section 3 - General Assembly NSM Workshop: Summarizes the co-design workshop held in the General Assembly (GenA) in Zagreb, highlighting its objectives, structure, participant engagement, and key insights that informed subsequent phases.
- ❖ Section 4 - Co-Design in the Action Phase: NSM Co-Creation and Prototyping: Describes the collaborative development of the NSMs through one-on-one meetings with pilot cities, co-creation sessions, and prototype team meetings. It also presents the first draft versions of the NSMs, reflecting the iterative design process.
- ❖ Section 5 - Technical Development Overview: Outlines the updated, newly introduced and unimplemented requirements, the different development phases, the user interface design and the technologies that are used in the platform.

- ❖ Section 6 - Upscaling and Validation Phase: Refinement, Testing, and Dissemination: Covers the activities aimed at expanding the reach and impact of the NSM platform. This includes feedback workshops, testing and validation with students, the creation of tutorial videos for the Massive Online Open Course (MOOC) and outreach efforts to other cities via sister projects.
- ❖ Section 7 - Public Launch of Neutrality Story Maps: Details the public launch of the NSM platform, including communication and outreach strategies.
- ❖ Section 8 - Analysis of Final NSMs and Behavior Change Potential: Analyses the final versions of the NSMs, assessing their potential to influence citizen behavior and support climate action.
- ❖ Section 9 - Reflections and Conclusions: Reflects on the overall co-design journey, synthesizing lessons learned, challenges encountered, and recommendations for future participatory digital storytelling initiatives.
- ❖ References
- ❖ Annex

2 Methodology

The methodology for developing the NSM platform followed a two-round co-design process that progressed from conceptual development to operational implementation. While the first round (M14-M18) focused on defining user requirements and producing initial mock-ups, the second round (M22-M36) aimed to operationalize the platform within each pilot city's local context. The second round therefore sought to ensure that each city would have a functioning and content-rich NSM by M36. This phase began with preparatory meetings held between M19 and M21, during which VUB and CERTH re-engaged with the pilot cities to define how each city envisions using the platform moving forward.

The following sub-sections briefly summarize the activities of the first round of co-design and detail the specific activities of the second co-design phase, structured around the evolving needs of the pilot cities and the overarching goal of delivering fully operational NSMs by M36. For an overview of the whole process see Table 1.

2.1 Brief Recap of First Co-Design Round

The second iteration of co-design for the NSM platform builds directly on the foundations laid during the first round (M14-M18). In this initial phase, the conceptual and methodological framework for NSM was developed collaboratively, aligning the platform's vision with the diverse priorities of the ten pilot cities, forming an essential methodological foundation for the present deliverable.

Through a series of co-design activities, including workshops, interviews, and surveys, VUB and CERTH gathered a first set of user requirements. These informed the development of platform mock-ups, which were presented and discussed in a workshop during the Cities Knowledge Exchange event in Rotterdam in M18. This event marked a key milestone, as cities were introduced to the platform's core functionalities and invited to reflect on how it could support their local climate neutrality goals.

Following the workshop, cities selected one or more of the three usage options for the platform (as defined in [D6.6 - Neutrality Story Maps for Pilot Cities 1](#)) and began outlining their local implementation strategies. This phase established a shared foundation for the second round, ensuring that subsequent development was grounded in real-world needs and expectations.

2.2 Co-design Approach

While the second round of co-design builds directly on the foundations laid in the first, it represents a shift from conceptual development to contextual implementation. The first round (M14-M18) drew on established frameworks such as Maguire & Bevan (2002) and Bevan et al. (2016), which emphasize structured, iterative engagement to define usability, accessibility, and satisfaction criteria. These approaches provided a robust methodological basis for user requirements analysis through surveys, interviews, and workshops.

In contrast, the second round (M22-M36) maintains the participatory ethos but transitions toward co-creation and operationalization, where cities actively shape and populate their NSMs through training, prototyping, and feedback loops. This phase aligns more closely with recent conceptualizations of co-creation as a mode of collaborative urban governance that encourage place-based knowledge integration, social learning, and transformative capacity (Frantzeskaki et al., 2025). It also reflects the evolution of participatory design into more flexible, context-sensitive practices that accommodate diverse stakeholder roles and iterative engagement across multiple stages (Wacnik et al., 2025; Vargas et al., 2025). While the underlying principles remain consistent, namely stakeholder inclusion, iterative refinement, and contextual responsiveness, the second round marks a shift in focus. Instead of primarily defining what the platform should be, this phase introduces a more implementation-oriented

logic. The emphasis now lies in enabling cities to use the platform meaningfully within their local planning cycles.

2.3 Data Collection Methods

Data were collected through a combination of structured and semi-structured interactions designed to elicit both functional and experiential insights. These included one-on-one meetings with municipal staff and project leads, co-creation workshops with diverse stakeholder groups, a dedicated testing workshop, recurring prototype team meetings, and structured feedback forms. This multi-modal approach enabled the triangulation of qualitative data, capturing a rich picture of local priorities, user expectations, and technical constraints.

In addition to verbal and written feedback, cities contributed draft content and visual materials for their NSMs. These served as both inputs for platform refinement and as boundary objects that facilitated dialogue between technical teams and city stakeholders (Star & Griesemer, 1989). The iterative nature of data collection allowed for continuous validation of assumptions and progressive alignment between user needs and platform capabilities.

2.4 Stakeholder Engagement

The second round of co-design included an expansion of the stakeholder ecosystem by onboarding new pilot cities and engaging students in a workshop co-facilitated by Delft University of Technology (TU Delft). Within the context of the urban planning process students are considered to be a vulnerable and often underrepresented group (Vargas et al., 2025). Furthermore, the original stakeholders were re-engaged to ensure continuity in participation.

To operationalize this expanded stakeholder ecosystem, engagement strategies were tailored to each city's governance structure, digital maturity, and community dynamics. Municipal staff, local citizens, and technical partners were involved through targeted outreach, facilitated workshops, and collaborative content development sessions. This context-sensitive approach helped promote trust, increase ownership, and ensure that the platform remained adaptable to diverse urban realities. This new active engagement process also reflected a shift from consultation to co-creation, where stakeholders were not only informants but active contributors to the platform's evolution.

2.5 Second Co-Design Round

To implement the second-round methodology, four interlinked activities were designed and executed as structured methods for supporting local adaptation, capacity-building, and iterative testing. These activities were:

1. **Training sessions:** to familiarize city teams with the platform's updated features. These included new content modules, visualization tools, and back-end functionalities. These sessions also served to build local capacity for autonomous platform use.
2. **Co-creation workshops:** to provide a collaborative space for cities to develop and structure their NSM content. The purpose of these sessions was to encourage collaboration within municipalities and to promote peer learning across cities.
3. **Prototype team meetings:** Prototype meetings were monthly sessions (July 2024-February 2025) where project partners supported cities in creating their pilot prototype, including an NSM draft. These meetings served to create agile feedback loops, where technical and design issues were discussed. These meetings enabled rapid iteration and ensured that user feedback was directly translated into platform improvements.

4. **Iterative refinement:** was achieved through structured user testing and feedback loops. Cities were invited to test early versions of their NSMs, provide feedback on usability and relevance, and suggest improvements. This iterative process ensured that the platform evolved in response to real-world use cases.

These activities were coordinated by VUB and CErTH, with support from other consortium partners where relevant. The coordination model emphasized responsiveness, flexibility, and distributed ownership, aligning with best practices in participatory technology development.

2.6 Preparatory Meetings

Between M19 and M21, VUB and CErTH conducted preparatory meetings with each pilot city to reintroduce the NSM platform and co-define local implementation strategies. These meetings helped identify city-specific needs and constraints and clarify intended usage scenarios.

Importantly, these meetings also facilitated the re-engagement of stakeholders from the first round and the onboarding of new participants from cities that had not previously been involved. This ensured a smooth transition into the second phase of co-design and reinforced the platform’s commitment to inclusivity, continuity, and responsiveness.

Table 1: Overview of Co-Design Activities

Co-design Round	Timing	Method	Purpose	Format	Participants
Round 1	M15-M16	Survey	Gather contextual information about cities requirements, expectations and current strategies.	Open and closed questions via qualtrics	All cities
	M16	Group Interviews (N=3)	Identify user needs, motivations, barriers, and potential synergies between the platform and the partner’s vision.	Online on Microsoft Teams (90 minutes)	Muenster, Budapest, Thessaloniki
	M18	Cities Knowledge Exchange Workshop	Feedback on the mockups and collaborative ideation.	In person: live annotation of mock-ups, scenario-based discussions, and collective prioritization exercises using tools such as Mentimeter .	All cities

	M18	Post-workshop follow-up survey	Feedback on the mock ups and additional city-level user requirements.	Open and closed questions via qualtrics	All cities
	M19-M21	Preparatory Meetings for the 2 nd round of co-design	To align cities on NSM use and prepare for the second co-design round.	Online on Microsoft Teams	All cities
Round 2	M22	General Assembly Workshop Zagreb	Showcase the first coded version of the tool, gather feedback, and train cities to create their first digital story.	In person: training session followed by Q&A session, gathering feedback on Mentimeter.	All cities
	M22	Post-workshop follow-up survey	Consolidate feedback and address outstanding questions.	Open and closed questions via qualtrics	All cities
	M27-M33	Feedback Workshops (N=3)	Provide structured feedback on the first version of the cities' digital stories.	Online on Microsoft Teams	All cities
	M31	TU Delft Workshop	Ensure the platform is responsive to the needs and aspirations of young adults, considered a vulnerable group.	In person: presentation of the platform, testing in small groups, students provide feedback in real-time	65 students

3 General Assembly NSM Workshop

The NSM session held during the UP2030 GenA in Zagreb (15-17 October 2024) was a key milestone in the co-design process. It brought together city representatives and project partners to review the platform's progress, participate in training, and provide feedback to guide future development.

3.1 Training

The training session, led by CERTH and VUB, introduced cities to the first coded version of the NSM platform including the homepage and story-building functionalities. Participants were guided through the process of selecting layouts, integrating multimedia elements, and publishing content. While the session was informative, it also revealed areas where further clarification was needed. For instance, several cities expressed confusion about the distinction between a “story” and a “homepage,” prompting the decision to develop a glossary of terms to support future onboarding (see Section 5.2.4).

Questions also arose around workflow expectations, specifically, whether the first story drafts would be developed by the project team or by the cities themselves. This highlighted the need for clearer documentation and visual templates to support content planning. Additionally, concerns about image copyright and media usage led to discussions about including disclaimers during user registration and providing curated lists of copyright-free resources.

Figure 1: General Assembly NSM Workshop in Zagreb

3.2 Participants Feedback

City feedback reflected a wide range of priorities and local constraints. Zagreb, for example, expressed satisfaction with the current NSM version and requested clustering features. Moreover, due to the upcoming election year, they opted to not enable citizen comments. Rotterdam showed interest in incorporating audio elements such as podcast snippets but found video integration less feasible. Granollers questioned the necessity of audio in citizen stories, while Muenster requested clearer guidance and templates to support their content development process.

The topic of maps generated particular interest. Milan suggested embedding maps at strategic points within scrollytelling articles, and several cities including Thessaloniki, Granollers, and Lisbon confirmed they had map layers they wished to integrate. Others, such as Budapest and Istanbul, indicated they did not currently have relevant geospatial data. These insights underscored the need for flexible integration options and compatibility with various map formats. While most cities were hesitant to enable public comments, some expressed interest in moderated or keyword-filtered systems. The “like” and “share” features received tentative support, though no strong consensus emerged.

Figure 2: General Assembly NSM Workshop in Zagreb

3.3 Post-Workshop Survey

To consolidate feedback and address outstanding questions, a follow-up survey was distributed to all participating cities. The results provided a clearer picture of cities' readiness to integrate geospatial content into their NSMs. Most cities reported having map layers in formats such as SHP, KML, and JPEG while several also confirmed the use of hosting platforms like [ArcGIS](#) and local Geographic Information System (GIS) setups (e.g. [QGIS](#)), which will inform the platform's technical development and ensure compatibility with existing municipal systems. Moreover, the survey also gathered input on registration preferences, moderation tools, and content management workflows. These responses guided the next iteration of platform development.

4 Co-Design in the Action Phase: NSM Co-Creation and Prototyping

During the action phase (M13-M26) each city, with support from its prototype team (see section 4.1.1), was expected to deliver a detailed description of its proposed pilot prototype, outlining the concept, intended functionality, and relevance to local climate neutrality goals. In UP2030, a city prototype refers to a strategic, co-designed model or framework that a city develops to guide its transition toward climate neutrality by 2030.

As with the first round of co-design, VUB and CERTH streamlined the timeline for this second round of co-design with project activities and milestones. The deadline for the first draft of NSM was in this case the same as the deadline for the city prototype, i.e. February 2025.

4.1 Co-Creation Sessions

Between September 2024 and February 2025, VUB and CERTH led a series of co-creation activities with the aim of developing the first draft of the NSM for each pilot city. These activities were embedded within the broader framework of prototype team meetings and were further complemented by targeted one-on-one sessions with pilot cities, allowing for tailored support and troubleshooting where necessary. In the case of Belfast, for example, an additional dedicated co-creation process focused specifically on the development of personas, involving iterative engagement with citizens, city representatives, and project partners to ensure local relevance and inclusivity.

The co-creation sessions were built directly on the outcomes of the first round of co-design (see [D6.6 - Neutrality Story Maps for Pilot Cities 1](#)), supporting cities as they took concrete steps toward creating and uploading content on the NSM platform. Collaboration with UP2030 technical partners and other stakeholders was essential throughout this phase, ensuring that both technical and contextual requirements were addressed.

4.1.1 Prototype Team Meetings

The monthly pilot implementation meetings were expanded to include the prototype team. Each pilot city had a dedicated prototype team composed of city liaisons, technical partners, and WP leaders, with a core objective to guide cities through the prototyping process and ensure coherence with the broader project goals. The prototype teams were composed of city representatives and liaisons, DRAXIS (as team lead, coordinating milestones and agendas), technical partners supporting implementation, an Engagement Taskforce partner, Universitat Politècnica de València (UPV) (for Key Performance Indicator (KPI) validation), VUB and CERTH (leading NSM development), and Thomas Stellmach Planning & Architecture (TSPA) (ensuring continuity from the Vision and Adaptive Pathways phases). Additional support was provided by Resilient Cities Network (RCities) (facilitating workshops linked to WP4 and Milestone 13), I-Catalist (ICA) (integrating the action phase into the Learning Action Alliance (LAA) process), TU Delft (as WP3 leader), and DRAXIS, Centro de Investigación de Recursos y Consumos Energéticos (CIRCE), University of Cambridge (UCAM), and TU Delft as WP3 task leaders.

VUB and CERTH played a central role in these teams, specifically leading the development and integration of the NSM tool by facilitating co-creation activities, supporting cities in content development, and ensuring that the tool remained adaptable to local contexts.

These monthly meetings between July 2024 and February 2025, served as a dynamic space for iterative development, where cities could raise questions, share progress, and receive tailored support on NSM related tasks. They were also used by VUB and CERTH to provide guidance on storytelling strategies and platform usability while addressing technical and conceptual challenges raised by cities.

4.1.2 Persona Development: Belfast

In line with VUB and CERTH’s approach to tailor the co-creation process to each city’s priorities, needs, and local engagement strategies, Belfast was the only city where the co-creation process centered on developing the NSM platform by incorporating additional stories from the perspectives of personas that reflect the diversity and needs of the local community. This process involved a series of iterative workshops and interviews with citizens, city officials, and project partners. The personas were designed to capture the goals, barriers, and motivations of different citizen profiles, ensuring that the content on the platform would be both inclusive and contextually relevant.

The persona development followed a four-step methodology adapted from Mulder & Yaar (2006):

1. Identify goals (what citizens want), behaviors (how they currently act), and attitudes or perceptions (how they view the issue or themselves in relation to it).
2. Cluster these insights into segments.
3. Test different segment combinations to refine and finalize persona profiles.
4. Humanize the personas by assigning names, key differentiators, and additional attributes.

VUB provided a persona profile template to the city of Belfast, which was distributed during community events such as the Open Botanic event. Citizens were invited to complete the template, sharing their knowledge, goals, barriers, and motivations related to climate neutrality, specifically in the three pilot focus areas: greening, active travel, and retrofitting.

The collected data was analyzed by VUB using [MAXQDA](#), a qualitative data analysis software. Responses were coded into variables such as barriers to behavior change, knowledge of climate neutrality, daily impacts of climate change, future visions, and preferred awareness methods. The interaction between these codes was examined to identify distinct persona profiles. After testing various combinations, the variables ‘behavior change’ and ‘climate impact on daily life’ emerged as the most insightful for segmentation (see Figure 3).

Figure 3: Persona Segments

The city of Belfast then further developed these profiles by assigning names and visual identities using generative AI ([ChatGPT](#)). These personas were validated in subsequent community events, where citizens confirmed that the profiles accurately reflected local needs. The process resulted in four distinct persona profiles (see Table 2).

Table 2: Belfast Persona Profiles

Persona:	The sceptic	The aspiring active traveler	The adaptive adjuster	The health-conscious guilty adapter
Motivators	Seasonal changes affect their enjoyment of traditional activities but don't feel direct personal impact.	Acknowledges changing weather patterns as a sign of climate change. Feels guilt about pollution and its impact on public health.	Responding to visible weather fluctuations and rising energy bills.	Driven by a desire to reduce personal guilt and improve collective health. Protects their own health and that of loved ones by adopting greener habits.
Barriers	Limited knowledge or skepticism about climate neutrality. High costs of retrofitting with no clear incentives (e.g., for buying energy-efficient boilers). Unsafe roads discourage active travel.	Public transport is inconvenient, unreliable, and expensive. Lack of infrastructure for active travel, such as bike lanes, parking, and pedestrian spaces.	Few or no financial incentives for retrofitting homes or adopting green technologies. Green alternatives (e.g., electric vehicles or solar panels) are unaffordable.	Lack of green spaces and limited organized community activities like litter picking or recycling schemes. Public transport options are limited and not user-friendly.
Support Needed	Engaging and accessible social media campaigns on climate neutrality. Offline community events like workshops, community gardens, and local fairs to foster learning and connection. Safer infrastructure for walking and biking and improved public transport accessibility.	Educational campaigns (e.g., videos) on sustainable practices like recycling and renewable energy use. Investment in safe biking infrastructure and reduced car dominance in cities. Subsidized or improved public transportation systems.	Subsidies or financial incentives for retrofitting and renewable energy adoption. Public demonstrations or open days to test electric vehicles or bikes. Community workshops on sustainable living practices.	Social media campaigns showcasing success stories and best practices in sustainability. Adult-focused clubs and events to encourage green practices collectively. Financial incentives like tax breaks for retrofitting and green transportation.

The use of personas in Belfast's NSM development significantly enhanced the potential for emotionally resonant and locally grounded digital storytelling, which is crucial for inspiring behavior change. Personas serve as fictional yet research-based representations of real user segments, enabling designers and policymakers to empathize with diverse community needs and tailor interventions accordingly (Jansen et al., 2021). By embedding personas into the storytelling process, the city was able to move beyond abstract climate messaging and instead communicate through relatable narratives that reflect lived experiences, motivations, and barriers. This approach aligns with research showing that digital storytelling can influence human behavior by engaging audiences at emotional and subconscious levels, fostering deeper connections and receptivity to change (Ersoy, 2025). Moreover, personas designed for social good have been shown to support inclusive engagement by representing marginalized voices and contextualizing climate impacts through intersectional lenses (Han & Wei, 2021).

4.2 First Draft of Neutrality Story Maps

By February 2025 (M26), 5 pilot cities successfully delivered a first draft of their NSM, reflecting the outcomes of the co-creation sessions and prototype team meetings. These drafts served as a foundation for further development and testing in the subsequent phases of the project.

The drafts varied in scope and format, shaped by local context, available data, and level of stakeholder engagement. In some cases, cities focused on narrative mapping of climate neutrality pathways, while others emphasized visual storytelling or integration with existing urban platforms.

All 5 pilot cities kept their preferred options to use the platform which they chose in the preparatory meetings that took place from M19 to M21. While the strategic approach is still the same, the content of the stories evolved (see section 2.2.5 in [D6.6 - Neutrality Story Maps for Pilot Cities 1](#)):

Granollers' NSM homepage tells the story of its journey within UP2030, moving from an initial vision to adaptive pathways that shape the city's climate-neutral future. The narrative emphasizes co-creation and community involvement, showcasing how local voices informed decision-making. Interactive maps, workshop snippets, and before-and-after photos illustrate how ideas translated into tangible actions, reinforcing the city's commitment to participatory climate planning.

Istanbul's NSM focuses on the risks climate change poses to the city, framing the urgency through data-driven storytelling. Graphs and statistics highlight vulnerabilities such as rising temperatures due to high CO2 emissions, while AI-generated images depict a climate-neutral future that contrasts starkly with current challenges. The story connects scientific evidence with aspirational visuals, inviting citizens to imagine and work toward a resilient urban landscape.

Muenster's NSM presents a narrative centered on climate challenges and solutions, detailing both ongoing initiatives and future possibilities. The homepage uses maps, photographs, and before-and-after simulations to show how interventions can transform the cityscape. By combining technical insights with visual storytelling, Muenster underscores its proactive stance in addressing climate risks and fostering sustainable urban development.

Milan's NSM explores the impact of climate change on urban heat and heat islands, focusing on the critical role of greenery in cooling the city. The narrative highlights strategies for expanding green infrastructure and mitigating heat stress, supported by maps and imagery that illustrate potential transformations. Milan's approach links environmental action with public health and livability, framing greening as a cornerstone of climate resilience.

Belfast's NSM homepage frames climate adaptation and justice through three priorities: greening, active travel, and retrofitting. Targeting central neighborhoods like the Linen Quarter, Sandy Row, and Donegall Pass, the story addresses flooding, air pollution, and infrastructure challenges. It integrates

strategies such as the Resilience Strategy and Net Zero Carbon Roadmap, complemented by maps, photos, and interactive visuals to connect climate action with community well-being and equity.

Cities engaged with the development of NSM at different speeds, reflecting the variety of organizational structures and participation strategies across the consortium. As a result, some cities finalized their first drafts in the next phase of the project, ensuring that their NSM aligns closely with their local priorities, stakeholder engagement timelines, and ongoing internal developments.

5 Technical Development Overview

Technical development evolved gradually as cities shared their needs, priorities and challenges throughout the project. This process led to adjustments in requirements, the adoption of additional technologies and the development of several improved versions of the platform.

5.1 Requirements

During the first-round of co-design activities, group interviews were conducted with the three cities Budapest, Muenster, and Thessaloniki, as well as online surveys and the workshop during the Cities Knowledge Exchange event in Rotterdam. Together with the first meetings with cities held at the start of the second co-design round, these activities resulted in a comprehensive list of user requirements, which were then prioritized using the MoSCoW method (Clegg & Barker, 1994). These requirements are described in detail in the previous deliverable [D6.6 - Neutrality Story Maps for Pilot Cities 1](#).

However, a set of requirements is not something rigid. It often evolves in response to new circumstances and the changing needs of stakeholders, in this case, the cities, and the feedback received as they use the actual tool. Consequently, during the remainder of the second round of co-design activities, the GenA workshop, and the period leading up to the end of the project, several requirements changed priority, and new ones were introduced.

Most of the requirements with a priority of “Should” or higher were implemented, along with a few “Could” requirements that were easy to realize. The following sections describe the requirements whose priority has been updated, the new requirements and those that have not yet been implemented. The complete table with the updated requirements can be found in Annex 1: Requirements List.

5.1.1 Updated Requirements

During the continued interaction with the cities, several requirements were reassessed as their feedback provided a clearer understanding of their actual needs and expectations from the tool. In addition, some requirements evolved in response to changes in how the cities envisioned using the tool. Table 3 presents the requirements that changed priority, along with their ID and both the previous and updated priorities.

Table 3: List of updated requirements and their new priorities

ID	Requirement	Priority
5.2	Template for creating and editing the homepage	Could → Must
1.2	Provide proof that they live in the city	Could → Won't
1.9	Create tags	Should → Won't
3.4	Limit of stories under a thread	Could → Won't
2.22	Creator username should not be visible in the story	Should → Won't
2.10	Text prompts for stories	Should → Could
3.5	Connection of threads with resources	Should → Could
2.24	Cities should approve each story before publishing it	Could → Should

6.12	Cities can add extra layers on the map	Could → Should
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One of the first and most significant changes concerned requirement 5.2, “Template for creating and editing the homepage.” Initially, the plan was for each city to decide the format and content of its homepage, after which CERTH would implement it as a static page. This approach was considered sufficient at first, as the homepage was not expected to require frequent updates. However, during the second round of co-design, it became evident that this solution lacked flexibility and was not intuitive for the cities. Cities could choose the design and provide content for the homepage pages, but any subsequent modification required them to contact CERTH again.

To address this issue, and after discussions between the VUB and CERTH, it was decided to develop a dedicated page, with real time content preview, where cities could create and edit their homepages directly. Although this change required additional time for design and implementation, it was identified as a critical improvement for the tool’s success, and its priority was upgraded from “Could” to “Must”. Furthermore, since the processes for creating homepages and stories were quite similar, it was realized that the new interface could replace the older, less user-friendly story creation page. This meant that developing the new homepage editor would enhance the tool in two ways: by giving cities autonomy over their homepage and by significantly improving the experience of creating stories. Since the homepage follows almost the same format as stories, the content-related requirements defined for stories also apply to the homepage.

Beyond requirement 5.2, several other requirements were revised following further discussions and feedback from the cities. Some were deprioritized or discarded entirely, while others gained importance as cities’ needs became clearer.

A few requirements were dropped due to limited value or feasibility. Requirement 1.2 “Provide proof that they live in the city” was removed (from “Could” to “Won’t”). This would require users to submit proof that they live in the city during registration, with each city deciding what type of proof to request. However, this approach would have placed an excessive administrative burden on the cities, raised privacy concerns, and excluded users such as tourists from participating in the tool. Similarly, requirement 1.9, “Create tags,” (from “Should” to “Won’t”) was dismissed as it would allow users to create their own tags, which could create moderation challenges for cities, user confusion due to overlapping or redundant tags, and additional technical complexity without providing sufficient added value. The same decision was made for 3.4 “Limit of stories under a thread” (from “Could” to “Won’t”), since imposing a limit provided no practical advantage. Finally, 2.22 “Creator username should not be visible in the story” (from “Should” to “Won’t”) was dropped, as displaying the author’s username was not considered a privacy issue and contributed to authenticity.

Other requirements were downgraded in priority. Requirement 2.10 “Text prompts for stories” (from “Should” to “Could”) was reconsidered, as its usefulness for supporting users remained uncertain and it was unclear whether prompts would help or feel awkward. Similarly, 3.5 “Connection of threads with resources” (from “Should” to “Could”) was lowered in priority because few cities expressed interest in using threads, and its added value for most cities was therefore limited.

Finally, two requirements were upgraded. Requirement 2.24 “Cities should approve each story before publishing it” (from “Could” to “Should”) became more important, since it allows cities to manage published content more effectively and prevent inappropriate stories from becoming public. Likewise, requirement 6.12, “Cities can add extra layers on the map,” was recognized as an important feature, as it allows cities to enrich the map with additional layers such as neighborhood boundaries or points of interest. This makes the map more informative, context-specific, and engaging for users.

5.1.2 [New Requirements](#)

Besides the changes in priority described above, several new requirements were introduced during the second round of co-design. All new requirements with a priority higher than “Could”, as well as

requirement 4.3 and 6.19 (“Could” priority), have already been implemented. Table 4 lists the new requirements and their priorities.

Table 4: List of new requirements and their priorities

ID	Requirement	Priority
1.14	Delete their account along with all associated data	Must
2.27	Stories contain maps	Must
2.28	Stories contain before-after image comparison module	Should
2.29	Navigation to next story from the story view page	Should
2.30	Ability to add text on images to provide credit or information	Could
2.31	Ability to format text and add hyperlinks	Must
2.32	Map comparison module	Could
2.33	Desktop and mobile preview of story during creation	Could
3.6	Thread end date	Could
4.3	Support all media types available for stories	Could
5.3	Page numbering	Could
5.4	Connection with stories	Should
6.14	Draft saving for content	Should
6.15	Notifications	Should
6.16	City council logo next to each city name	Could
6.17	Draw custom layers on map	Should
6.18	Add ArcGIS layer on the map	Should
6.19	Dark theme	Could

One of the essential features added to the platform was the ability for a user to delete their account along with all data associated with it (requirement 1.14). This functionality is necessary for General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) compliance, as the regulation gives users the right to request the erasure of their personal data (“right to be forgotten”). With this feature in place, users can now permanently delete their account, and all personalized data linked to it (such as their stories) is automatically removed from the platform.

To strengthen the mapping aspect of the tool, maps were added to stories and the homepage (requirement 2.27). Maps make the stories and homepage more interactive and serve as a rich media type that can visualize important information and context. Requirement 2.28 introduced a before-after

image comparison module. From the cities' perspectives, the tool is often used to showcase the activities or work they have carried out, and this feature is particularly useful for presenting before-and-after cases in a visually engaging way.

Emphasis was also given to improving navigation between stories. When a user reaches the final page of a story in the story view, they can now move directly to the next story chronologically using a dedicated button, without returning to the timeline (requirement 2.29). Cities also requested the ability to place text on top of an image in both the homepage and stories (requirement 2.30), mainly for providing credits or add context about the depicted place.

Another important enhancement was the ability to format text (bold, italics, underline, color, alignment) (requirement 2.31). This gives cities more control over how their content is presented, allowing them to highlight key information, improve readability, and structure their narrative in a clearer way. This requirement also introduced support for hyperlinks, which indirectly helped fulfil requirement 5.4 by enabling the homepage to link directly to specific stories. Users can now include story URLs inside homepage text or within other stories, allowing smooth navigation between related content.

There was also a suggestion to introduce a map comparison module (requirement 2.32). The concept behind this feature is to allow users to place two different map layers on top of each other and compare them using a sliding control.

Finally, requirement 2.33 suggested adding a mobile and desktop preview option inside the story-creation page (requirement 2.33), allowing users to check the mobile or desktop appearance of their story while they are creating it.

For threads, requirement 3.6 gives the option to define an end date for a thread, after which no new stories can be submitted. This feature helps cities better manage time-bound discussions or campaigns.

Concerning resources, requirement 4.3 suggested supporting all media types available for stories. Since this required little effort and ensured consistency across content types, it was implemented even though it had a "Could" priority.

For the homepage, requirement 5.3 proposed adding page numbers. This helps users orient themselves within longer homepages and improves the reading experience, especially when the content includes many sections.

A key addition was the possibility to save content as a draft before publishing it (requirement 6.14). Initially, content could only be published, but now users can create and save their work, return to it later, and edit it before publishing. This makes the content creation process more flexible and user friendly. Another important improvement was the introduction of a notification system within the tool (requirement 6.15), which alerts users about relevant actions, such as a story awaiting approval or a user requesting a role upgrade.

Some cities also suggested displaying the city council logo next to each city name (requirement 6.16) to reinforce authenticity and strengthen the connection between the platform and the local administration.

Requirements 6.17 and 6.18 introduced additional mapping capabilities beyond simple layer uploads. Requirement 6.17 added support for drawing custom layers directly on the map, while requirement 6.18 introduced support for displaying layers hosted on the [ArcGIS](#) platform, allowing cities to integrate data already available in their existing GIS systems.

Finally, requirement 6.19 concerned the addition of a dark theme. This requirement is tied to accessibility and supports the broader requirement of making the platform more inclusive by offering more comfortable viewing options for users with visual sensitivities or preferences for low-light environments.

5.1.3 Unimplemented Requirements

A few requirements were not implemented in the current version of the tool. These include all requirements with a “Won’t” priority, as well as all those related to comments. Although the main “Comments” requirement had a “Could” priority, some of the related ones, such as limits on comment length or reporting functionality, had been initially assigned higher priorities by mistake. To ensure consistency, all comment-related requirements were downgraded to “Could”. In addition, a few other requirements with a “Could” priority were not implemented. If time allows before the end of the project, some of these may still be developed. Table 5 lists all the requirements that were not implemented and have a “Could” priority or higher.

Table 5: List of unimplemented requirements (with Could or higher priority)

ID	Requirement	Priority
2.12	Comments	Could
1.8	Report comments	Could
1.11	Limit on number of comments under a story	Could
1.12	Limit on number of comments in a given timeframe	Could
2.13	Comment length limit	Could
2.25	Cities should be able to disable comments	Could
1.3	Provide information such as age, gender etc	Could
2.30	Ability to add text on images to provide credit or information	Could
2.32	Map comparison module	Could
2.33	Desktop and mobile preview of story during creation	Could
3.6	Thread end date	Could
4.2	Different resources categories	Could
5.3	Page numbering in home page	Could
6.8	The tool should be available for a neighborhood	Could
6.11	Different basemaps for the map	Could
6.16	Add city council logo next to each city name	Could

5.2 NSM Platform

The NSM platform is a web-based mobile-friendly application designed to help cities communicate their climate actions and engage citizens through storytelling and mapping. It consists of four main building blocks: Stories, Homepage, Threads, and Resources.

A story is a multimedia narrative composed of a limited number of pages in a scrollytelling format, each of which can contain text, media, maps, or a combination of these. Every story is geotagged so that it can be displayed on a map. In the context of both stories and the homepage, a page is a full-screen section with its own design. Both cities and citizens can create stories, with citizens having access to a more simplified set of capabilities. The stories are displayed in a timeline together with a map that shows pins indicating their location.

The homepage serves as the entry point where each city presents its local context and vision for climate neutrality. It follows a scrollytelling format similar to stories but offers more flexibility in page design, has no limit on the number of pages, and can only be created by the city.

Stories can be submitted under threads (topics) defined by the city, while resources are more static, article-like entries that allow cities to share important information such as guides, reports or educational material.

Stories, threads, and resources can all be associated with tags defined by the city, which act as descriptive keywords related to their content.

5.2.1 [Versions](#)

The NSMs platform was developed through an iterative process, building on the preliminary version presented in [D6.6 - Neutrality Story Maps for Pilot Cities 1](#). This preliminary version included only the very basic functionalities such as a simple login-signup workflow, story creation, and city selection. Throughout the project, the platform evolved, with each new version introducing new functionalities or refining existing elements. The next sections outline these versions and the key changes they introduced.

5.2.1.1 [1st Version, GenA Workshop](#)

This version focused on implementing the new requirement for a dedicated page to create a homepage dynamically. The goal was to have the core functionality of this requirement ready for the GenA workshop in October 2024 (M22), where it would be presented for the first time.

The first step was to design this new page so it would be flexible enough to support different page types and media, and easy to extend in the future. It was also designed in a modular way so that the common elements could also be used in the new story creation page. This page features real-time preview of the content, support for all five available page layouts, support for images as the first implemented media type, and simple text inputs for adding text. The story-creation page was updated to follow the same design.

Finally, the homepage was implemented to present the created content using scrollytelling animations, and the platform was adapted to display properly on mobile devices.

5.2.1.2 [2nd Version, Action Phase](#)

The second version was developed after the GenA workshop and continued until December (M24), when the commitment had been made to deliver the first version that cities could use to create content, including the main workflow for creating and publishing both the homepage and stories, along with the essential required functionalities.

During this phase, the homepage and story creation pages were finalized and further improved. The page layouts were also refined and enriched with more design options. Support for video, audio and before-after image comparison was added as new media types. A new rich text editor was introduced and refined, supporting text formatting and link insertion. Finally, the platform was updated to save and load stories using the new format, and the story view page was adapted to work with the updated structure.

5.2.1.3 3rd Version, First Cities Prototype

Development of the third version started in December 2024 (M24) and continued until the end of February (M26), when the cities had to complete their first prototype. The focus during this period was to add support for maps in stories and the homepage, and to improve the platform's authentication system.

Therefore, in this version support for maps was added, offering three options: drawing layers on the map, uploading layers, or displaying maps from [ArcGIS](#). The signup and login flows were improved and made more robust, password reset and forgot-password functionalities were implemented, access to platform pages was adjusted based on user rights, and cities were given the ability to approve users requesting higher rights. The story-sharing functionality was also implemented. The library used for displaying maps was changed to [OpenLayers](#) (OLMaps), which offers free and unlimited use, unlike [Mapbox](#), which, although it offers a generous free tier, may not be sustainable in the long term if the number of users increases. Finally, the new story-creation page was further improved by adding the ability to select the story's location on the map.

5.2.1.4 4th Version, Upscaling Phase

The fourth version of the tool covers the period between February 2025 (M26) and the public launch of the platform at the end of October (M34). In this phase, the focus shifted from the core workflow of creating the homepage and stories to implementing the remaining features required for a complete platform. By the end of this period, the tool had reached a much more mature and complete state, ready for public use.

The work in this phase began with developing the pages for creating Threads and Resources, along with their corresponding view pages. Support for internationalization was added, enabling the platform to be translated into different languages. The authentication system was further improved with the ability to register using a Gmail account, email confirmation during registration, password change functionality, and additional checks during signup such as over-18 age confirmation and agreement to the privacy policy and terms and conditions. The security of the backend was also enhanced.

A new dashboard was introduced, offering pages for managing your stories, threads, and resources, approving citizens' stories before publication, adding images to the shared image gallery that users can use when creating content, defining tags, and managing the user profile, including changing username, email, and password, requesting a higher role, and deleting your account. Through the dashboard, cities can also add layers to the map that displays the stories.

The homepage and story creation pages were further improved, including refinements to the styling of the different page layouts. A new feature was introduced allowing users to save a homepage or story as a draft instead of publishing it directly. The story view page was updated to improve usability and make it more intuitive. A new feature was also added to allow text to be written on drawn map layers, along with the ability to edit an existing layer.

Stories shown on the timeline were connected to their corresponding pins on the stories map, allowing users to click a pin to find the story or navigate from a story to its pin. The backend was further strengthened, and pagination was implemented for the stories and threads timelines. Notifications inside the platform were also added so that users are informed about important actions.

Finally, a major accessibility feature was developed, allowing users to adjust text size, contrast, and other visual settings, and a dark theme was introduced.

5.2.1.5 Final Version

The final version covers the period from the public launch of the platform (M34) to the end of the project (M36). During this phase, the focus was on implementing a set of final improvements that further refined the user experience and implementing the remaining important functionalities.

A reporting functionality was added, allowing users to report inappropriate stories directly from the platform. Some layouts for the homepage and story pages were improved, and a number of bugs were fixed to ensure a smoother and more stable experience. In addition, filtering options were introduced for stories, allowing users to browse them more easily by selecting criteria such as tags. [Google Analytics](#) was integrated to provide insights into user activity and engagement, and translations were finalized across all supported languages.

5.2.2 User Interface

The NSM platform offers a user-friendly, intuitive, and mobile-friendly interface. When a user enters the platform at <https://m4d.services.iti.gr/up2030/app/>, the first page they see is the Homepage (Figure 4) of the selected city and can freely browse all public content without signing in. Connection is required only for creating content.

Every user is linked to a single city and can create content only for that city and is assigned one role. The platform supports three user roles

The platform supports three user roles. The first role is City Administrator. This is the highest role and can create and edit the homepage, stories, threads, and resources of their city, as well as manage all platform settings related to that city. This role can only be granted by CERTH and is reserved for municipal staff responsible for the city's NSM. The second role is City Organization. Users with this role can create stories, threads, and resources but cannot manage the homepage or perform administrative actions. To obtain this role, a user must submit a request through the platform and be approved by a City Administrator. City Organization can create stories, threads, and resources but does not have administrative rights. The default role for all new accounts is Citizen. Citizens can create stories, but these must be reviewed and approved by a City Administrator before they become public.

Most pages share common interface elements such as the header and the accessibility panel, which are described in the next section. After that, the following sections describe the authentication pages, Homepage, Stories, Threads, Resources, and the platform's Dashboard.

Figure 4: The NSM Platform

5.2.2.1 Global Interface Elements

The main content pages of the platform that are the Homepage, Stories, Threads and Resources, all feature the same navigation bar (Figure). This bar contains the main navigation and action elements for the platform. On the left of the bar, the UP2030 logo can be clicked to return to the homepage. Next to it, the city name indicates the city currently being viewed. Clicking it opens a list of all available UP2030 cities to switch between. When a different city is chosen, the interface updates to show the corresponding content.

This area is followed by the navigation tabs that lead to the four main sections: Homepage, Stories, Threads, and Resources. The Create button allows users to start creating content, depending on their role. The Notifications icon displays the latest updates relevant to the user. When new notifications are available, a badge appears showing their number, and clicking the icon opens a window with a detailed view of the notifications. The Profile button opens a menu showing the connected user’s basic information (username and email) and provides links to key dashboard pages and the option to sign out. If no user is connected, this button is replaced by a Sign-in button. The layout of the header is adjusted in mobile view to ensure proper display and usability (Figure).

Figure 5: Mobile view

The navigation bar on content-creation pages is simplified (Figure). It includes only the UP2030 logo, the name of the city for which the content is being created, a button for returning to the main platform, and the profile icon with its usual functionality.

The Accessibility panel that is usually displayed in the right bottom of the screen contains tools for enhancing the readability of the platform. Available options include adjusting text size, enabling negative or high contrast modes for better visibility, applying a grayscale filter, and restoring all settings to their default values.

5.2.2.2 User Authentication

To sign in to the application, users can click the “Sign In” button in the header. On the login page (Figure), they can connect either with their username and password or with a Gmail account, depending on how they registered.

The sign-in page features the UP2030 logo at the top. Below it is the heading "Sign in". There are two input fields: "Username *" and "Password *". The password field has an eye icon to toggle visibility. A green "Sign in" button is positioned below the fields. A link for "Forgot my password" is located below the "Sign in" button. Below this is a horizontal separator with the word "or" in the center. Underneath is a "Sign in with Google" button with the Google logo. At the bottom, there is a link "Don't have an account? Sign up" and a "Return Home" button.

Figure 6: Sign in Page

If the password has been forgotten, the “Forgot Password” option allows users to request to reset it by entering the email used during registration (Figure). A message is then sent to their inbox with a link for setting a new password. A “Return Home” button is also available to navigate back to the main platform.

The forgot password page features the UP2030 logo at the top. Below it is the heading "Forgot Password". A message reads: "Please enter the email that you registered with to receive an email with a password reset link." Below this is an "Email address *" input field. A green "Send email" button is positioned below the field. Below the button is a link "Back to Sign in" and a "Return Home" button.

Figure 7: Forgot Password Page

If a user does not yet have an account, they can select the “Sign Up” option. The Sign Up page (Figure) requires a username, an email address, and a password that meets the platform’s strength requirements. Users must also select their city, confirm that they are at least 18 years old, and accept the Terms and Conditions and Privacy Policy before completing the registration. Anyone who completes these steps can create an account. A confirmation email is then sent to verify the provided address, and once confirmed, the user can log in with their credentials.

Figure 8: Sign up Page

If users choose to register with a Gmail account, after selecting their Google profile they are redirected to a page (Figure) where they must select their city, confirm that they are over 18, and accept the Terms and Conditions and Privacy Policy. Completing this step is required to activate the account.

Figure 9: Complete Registration Page for Gmail Authentication

After registering, users can access their profile page (Figure) by clicking the profile icon in the navigation bar and selecting the “Profile” option. Users who registered with a username and password can change their username, email address, and password through this page. For accounts created through Google authentication, only the username can be modified. If a Google-registered user has not completed the required registration information, a “Complete Registration” button appears, leading them back to the page (Figure) where they must provide the remaining details to activate their account.

Figure 10: Profile Page

Lastly, Citizens have the option in the profile page to request the City Organization role, while all users can permanently delete their account and associated data from the platform through the “Delete Account” option.

5.2.2.3 Homepage

The homepage is the first page that a user sees when visiting a city’s page. Only users with the City Administrator role can create or edit the homepage. Once signed in, they can click the Create button in the header and select “New Homepage” (Figure 11), which opens the homepage creation page. If a homepage already exists, the option appears as “Edit Homepage”.

Figure 11: Modal for the Creation Pages

The homepage-creation page is divided into two sections: a real time preview of the homepage on the left and a sidebar on the right, which contains the tools for creating and designing the homepage (Figure). Using the sidebar, the first thing that a user can do is to add pages to the homepage using the Add Page button. Initially, a single blank page is provided by default. Pages appear in a list, where only one can be expanded at a time to show its inputs. Clicking on a page title expands or collapses it, and when expanded, the preview automatically scrolls to the corresponding page. Pages can be rearranged or deleted using the icons next to each page title.

Figure 12: Homepage Creation Page

For each page, the first step is to select a layout. Once a layout is chosen, the corresponding input fields appear. These inputs differ depending on the selected layout, but two categories are common across most layouts: text inputs and media selection.

The text input allows users to write and format their text using a simple set of formatting options, including choosing between three text sizes (small, normal, large), setting alignment, applying bold, italic, or underline styling, selecting a text color between five predefined options, and inserting links.

Media selection allows users to choose the media they want to add to the page. Five media types are supported, although not all layouts allow all types: image, video, audio, image comparison, and map. Images can be added either by uploading a file or by selecting one from the city's shared gallery. Videos and audio files can be uploaded directly, and in the case of audio, an additional image can be chosen to appear in place of the audio player. The image comparison option enables users to add two images that will be displayed with a movable slider to show a before–after effect.

Selecting “Map” as the media type opens three different options for adding map layers. “Draw Layers” allows users to draw points, polygons, lines, or circles directly on the map and customize each element with a color and an optional text label (Figure 13). “KML/Shapefile Layers” enables users to upload either a KML file or a ZIP file containing Shapefile data. Finally, the “ArcGIS Layers” option displays a map from [ArcGIS](#) simply by providing its id.

Figure 13: Draw Layers Modal

There are five different layout options available: Title Page, Text Page, Media Page, Media and Text Side by Side, and Media with Overlay Text Box. These layouts are described in detail below.

The title page (Figure) is primarily used as the opening or closing part of the homepage, or as a way to separate different sections. It includes a title, an optional subtitle, and a media element, which can be either an image or a video. Users can choose the position of the title and subtitle, as well as their color from the available color options. Two design variations are available: one where the media covers the entire page with the title and subtitle layered on top, and another where the media occupies the left half of the screen while the title and subtitle are placed on the right.

Figure 14: Title Page Layout

The Text Page (Figure) is a simple page that contains only a centered text element. Therefore, the only input for this layout is a text input that offers formatting options as it has been described above.

Figure 15: Text Page Layout

The Media Page layout (Figure) displays a single media element that fills the entire page. The media can be any of the supported types described earlier.

Figure 16: Media Page Layout

Another layout option is the Media and Text Side by Side (Figure). In this layout, the media and text are displayed next to each other, with the media occupying roughly two-thirds of the screen and the text the remaining space. Users can choose whether the media appears on the left or the right side. For the text section, multiple text entries can be added for the same media element, creating a scrolling effect where the text changes while the media remains fixed. All media types are supported in this layout. When an image is selected, an additional setting becomes available that allows users to choose whether the image should fit within the available space without cropping, while a blurred version of it appears in the background, or be zoomed to fully cover the entire area. This option is also available when selecting an image for an audio file.

Figure 17: Media and Text Side by Side Page Layout

The last layout option is Media with Overlay Text Box (Figure). In this layout, the media element covers the entire page, and a text box is placed on top of it. As with the previous layout, users can add multiple text entries for the same media element, creating the same effect where the media remains fixed while the text changes during scrolling. In addition to the text and media inputs, this layout also includes an option for selecting the position of the text box, with three choices available: left, center, or right.

Figure 18: Media with Overlay Text Box Page Layout

At the bottom of the sidebar, there is a Publish button with an arrow on its right side. Clicking the arrow reveals the Save option, which allows the homepage to be saved as a draft at any time. Publishing is only possible when all required fields have been completed. After saving or publishing, the page reloads, and if the homepage has been published, the button changes to Update.

On mobile devices, the layout of the homepage-creation page is adapted so that only one section is visible at a time: either the preview or the sidebar. By default, the sidebar is shown first, and users can switch to the preview by selecting the “Preview” button at the bottom as shown in Figure . When the preview is active, the same button changes to Close Preview, allowing users to return to the sidebar and continue editing.

Figure 19: Homepage Builder Page on Mobile View

When the homepage is published, it appears in the Home tab of the city (Figure) and is presented with scrollytelling animations. When two or more consecutive pages use the Media and Text Side by Side or Media with Overlay Text Box layouts, the media section remains fixed while the text scrolls. As the text of the next page enters the viewport, the media changes smoothly to one of the next pages.

For pages containing video or audio, playback begins automatically when the element becomes visible. In layouts where the media is displayed as a background, such as Title Page and Media with Overlay Text Box, videos are muted by default and have no visible controls. In contrast, in the Media Page and Media and Text Side by Side layouts, videos and audio elements include playback and volume controls and are not muted.

On mobile devices, the Media and Text Side by Side layout adjusts to the limited screen space by stacking the elements vertically, placing the media on top and the text below.

5.2.2.4 Stories

Stories can be created through the Create button by selecting the “New Story” option. The story-creation page follows the same structure as the homepage-creation page, with a real-time preview on the left and a sidebar on the right. Unlike the homepage, stories support only two layouts: Media and Text Side by Side and Media with Overlay Text Box. In addition, users with the Citizen role have access only to the Draw Layers option when adding a map.

The sidebar includes two tabs: Content and Information. The Content tab displays the list of pages, similar to the homepage, but with a limitation of five pages for citizens and eight for City Administrators. The Information tab contains the location field, which is mandatory, and optional fields for adding tags and submitting the story under an existing thread (Figure).

Figure 20: Story Builder page

At the bottom of the sidebar, users can Save the story as a draft or publish it. When a Citizen publishes a story, it moves to a pending state and must be approved by the City Administrator before becoming public. Only City Administrators can update their published stories.

Published and approved stories appear in the Stories page (Figure). Stories are shown in a timeline on the left, while their location pins appear on a map on the right. Hovering over a story highlights its pin on the map, and clicking a pin scrolls the timeline to the corresponding story and highlights it. City Administrators can also add layers to this map to be visible from all users as it is described in Section 5.2.2.7.

Figure 21: Stories Page

Each story preview includes buttons for liking and sharing. Liking requires the user to be signed in. A three-dot menu is available on stories owned by the connected user: Citizens can delete their stories, while City Administrators can both edit and delete them.

On smaller screens, the Stories page is split into two tabs: one showing the timeline and the other showing the map. In the map tab, selecting a pin opens a popup with the basic details of the story and a Show more button that opens the full story (Figure).

Figure 22: Stories Page on Mobile View

Clicking a story preview in the timeline opens it in full-screen mode (Figure). At the top of the screen, the story shows its author and publication date, along with a back arrow for returning to the previous page. The bottom of the screen includes the like, share, and three-dot buttons. Stories follow the same format as the homepage view and consist of multiple pages that can have different layouts. At the end of the story, there is a map that contains a pin indicating the story’s location, and when additional stories exist in the timeline, a down-arrow button allows users to move directly to the next story without going back.

Figure 23: Story Presentation Page

To help users manage the content they have created, the platform includes a My Stories page (Figure), accessible either from the profile menu or through the Dashboard. This page organizes a user's stories based on their publication status.

Figure 24: My Stories Page

For citizens, the page is divided into three sections: Published, Saved, and Pending. The Published section displays stories that have been approved by the City Administrator and are publicly available on the platform. The Saved section includes stories that have been created and stored as draft, while the Pending section lists those submitted but still awaiting approval from the City Administrator. For City Administrators, the page includes only the Published and Saved sections, as their stories are approved automatically.

On the My Stories page, the user’s stories are displayed in a list. Each story includes a three-dot icon in the top-right corner, which opens a menu with actions that depend on the user’s role and the story’s status. Citizens can edit or delete stories in the Saved section and only delete stories that are Published or Pending. City Administrators, however, can edit or delete stories in any state. Selecting Edit opens the story creation page with the existing content prefilled, while Delete permanently removes the story.

5.2.2.5 Threads

Threads are created through the Create button by selecting the “New Thread” option. In the thread creation page (Figure), users can fill in the main fields that define the thread, including the title, short and main description, thumbnail, location and other optional parts such as map layers and tags.

The screenshot shows the 'Thread Builder Page' interface. At the top, it says 'Create new Thread'. Below this are several input fields and buttons:

- Title ***: A text input field containing 't/' with a character limit of 0/30.
- Short Description ***: A larger text input field with a character limit of 0/140.
- Description ***: A rich text editor with a toolbar containing icons for Bold (B), Italic (I), Underline (U), and Link (🔗). The text area contains 'Text...' and has a character limit of 0/500.
- Thumbnail ***: A section with two buttons: 'Upload Image' (with a camera icon) and 'Gallery'. Below these is a large empty rectangular area for the thumbnail.
- Select Location ***: A button with a location pin icon and the text 'Select Location'.
- Map Layer**: A button with a plus sign and the text 'Add Layer'.
- Tags**: A dropdown menu with the text 'Add tags' and a downward arrow.

At the bottom right of the form, there are two buttons: 'Save' (light blue) and 'Publish' (purple). A small circular icon with a person silhouette is located in the bottom right corner of the page.

Figure 25: Thread Builder Page

The title defines the topic of the thread and cannot contain spaces, while the short description provides a quick overview of its focus and appears in the thread's preview. The main description is displayed on the thread's page and allows the use of some basic formatting options. Each text field also has its own character limit. The thumbnail image helps users quickly recognize the topic of the thread and can be uploaded directly from the user's computer or selected from the gallery. The location field sets the place the thread refers to and can be set by clicking on the map, where it appears as a pin. The last two optional fields are map layer and tags. The map layer adds extra information to the thread's map, highlighting specific areas by using the Draw Layer option or by uploading a KML or Shapefile file. Tags are created by the city and are used to associate the thread with those that are most relevant to its content.

During the creation process, the thread can either be saved or published. The Save option can be used at any time to store the current version of the thread, allowing the user to return and continue editing later. The Publish option makes the thread published on the platform, but it requires all mandatory fields to be filled.

After publication, the thread becomes visible on the Threads page (Figure), which provides an overview of those available within the selected city. Each thread is displayed as a preview card in the timeline and represented on the map as a pin. The preview includes the thread's title, thumbnail, short description, associated tags and the number of stories submitted under it. If the user is the owner of a thread, a three-dot menu appears on the right side of the preview card, providing options to edit or delete the thread. A search bar is also available at the top of the page, allowing threads to be easily located by their title. Clicking a pin on the map highlights the corresponding thread in the timeline and scrolls to its position, while hovering over a thread card changes its pin color for easier reference.

Figure 26: Threads Page

Selecting a specific thread opens its dedicated page, which again displays a timeline on the left and a map on the right (Figure). At the top of the timeline, there is an arrow next to the title that allows navigation back to the Threads page, along with the same three-dot menu available for the thread’s owner. Below this section, the thumbnail, main description, and associated tags are displayed, followed by the list of stories linked to that thread. Each story can be opened in full-screen, similar to the Stories page. On the map, the pins represent the stories associated with this specific thread and follow the same interaction behavior as on the Stories page. Any map layer added to the thread is also shown, offering further information.

Figure 27: Single Thread Page

As in the Stories page, the mobile view again presents the timeline and map as tabs and selecting a pin on the map opens a popup with basic information for each thread or on a single thread page, for each story.

To view and manage all threads created by a user, the Dashboard includes a page called My Threads (Figure). The page separates published threads, which are visible on the platform, from drafts that are still in progress and not yet published. Each thread includes a three-dot menu in the top-right corner, providing edit and delete options. The Edit option opens the thread creation page with the existing content already filled in allowing modifications, while the Delete option permanently removes the thread.

Figure 28: My Threads Page

5.2.2.6 Resources

Resources can be created from the Create button by selecting the “New Resource” option. In the builder page (Figure), users define the title, summary, thumbnail and main content, along with optional tags when relevant.

Figure 29: Resource Builder Page

The title defines the main subject of the resource, while the summary gives a brief idea of its content, helping users understand what the resource is about, with character limits applied to both. The thumbnail can be added from the gallery or a local upload and should be relevant to the resource’s

topic. The main content is structured through content blocks, which are added by selecting the desired type from the block selection panel (Figure). The available types include text, image, image comparison, video, audio, and map. Text blocks are the main part of the resource, as they explain the topic of the resource in detail. The media-type blocks add visual and interactive elements that make the resource more engaging, using the same input options as those available in other content creation pages within the platform. Blocks can be reordered using the up and down arrows or removed through the delete icon and each media-type block can support a caption with a character limit.

Figure 30: Content Section in Resource Builder Page

At any point during creation, the user can save their progress and continue later or complete all mandatory fields to make the resource publicly available.

When a resource is finalized and published, it becomes visible on the Resources page (Figure), which displays all available ones for the selected city in a grid layout. Each resource includes the thumbnail image, the author’s name, publication date, and the summary. If the connected user is the owner of a resource, a three-dot menu appears in the top-right corner, providing options to edit or delete it.

Figure 31: Resources Page

Selecting a resource opens its individual page (Figure). At the top, there is an arrow that allows navigation back to the Resources page, followed by the same details presented in the resource overview, with the summary displayed in bold. Below this section, the main content of the resource is shown in the format defined by the author, such as text, media or a combination, giving the page the appearance of a blog post or article. If the resource includes tags, they are displayed at the bottom of the page.

Figure 32: Single Resource Page

To view and manage their resources, users can access the “My Resources” page (Figure) within the Dashboard. This page separates published resources, which are available on the platform, from drafts that are still being edited. Each resource includes a three-dot menu, where selecting Edit opens the creation page with the existing content prefilled, while Delete permanently removes the resource.

Figure 33: My Resources Page

5.2.2.7 Dashboard

The Dashboard can be accessed through the profile menu located in the header. It serves as the main management area of the platform, presenting a sidebar on the left and the content area on the right.

In the sidebar on the left of the Dashboard, there are all the available pages. On the right, at the top there is a navigation bar that includes a Home button for returning to the platform and the profile icon.

Unlike other pages, the Dashboard does not display the main header, but its own navigation bar located in the content area, showing the title “Dashboard” on the left and on the right an “App” button that returns the user to the main part of the platform and the profile icon. The sidebar contains all the available Dashboard tabs, with the UP2030 logo displayed at the top. The available tabs differ depending on the user’s role. (Figure).

All users have access to the Profile, My Stories and Settings pages, while City Administrators have access to additional pages, including My Threads, My Resources, Pending Stories, Requests, Gallery, Tags, and Map Layer. Some of these pages have already been described in previous sections, so only the remaining ones will be covered here:

- Settings page: It includes the option to switch on the dark theme
- Pending Stories page: It lists stories submitted by Citizens that require approval. Selecting a story opens its presentation to view the story and then accept it for publication or decline it, in which case it is removed from the platform. (Figure)

Figure 34: Pending Stories Page

- Requests page: It allows users to review Citizens seeking the City organization role. (Figure)

Figure 35: Requests Page

- Gallery page: Through this page City Administrators can manage the shared image gallery for their city by either adding new images or removing. (Figure)

Figure 36: Gallery Page

- Tags page: Tags page (Figure) allows City Administrators to create and manage keywords. New tags can be added by typing a word and pressing enter, while existing ones can be removed. Once saved, the tags become available for all city users to include in their content.

Figure 37: Tags Page

- Map Layer page: It allows users to select or upload a map layer to highlight specific information within the city’s Stories page. The available options include creating a draw layer or uploading a KML/Shapefile. Once saved, the selected layer becomes visible on the city’s map view. (Figure)

Figure 38: Map Layer Page

5.2.3 Technologies

For the development of the web application, the JavaScript library [React](#) is used due to its component-based architecture, which facilitates modular and scalable development. Along with React, [Material UI](#) is used, a popular library that provides a wide range of ready-to-use user interface (UI) components. Material UI is useful for faster development and for providing components that adhere to the modern design principles. To manage the application's state more efficiently, especially as it scales, [Redux](#) is used. Redux centralizes the application's state, making it easier to manage complex state logic, reduce redundancy, and improve the predictability of state transitions within React.

The interactive maps in the application are powered by [OpenLayers](#) (OLMaps), an open-source mapping library that provides flexible tools for displaying map layers, drawing features, and integrating geospatial data without recurring costs or usage restrictions.

Scroll effects on the homepage and in stories are implemented using the [GSAP](#) library. GSAP enables smooth animations and interactive transitions that enhances the storytelling experience. In addition, the application integrates [Quill](#), a lightweight and customizable text editor, to provide rich-text editing functionality in content creation.

To collect usage analytics for the platform, [Google Analytics](#) is used. It was chosen because it is straightforward to integrate, widely adopted, and provides reliable insights into how users interact with the application.

Data storage and content management are handled using [Strapi](#), a powerful, open-source Node.js headless CMS. Strapi uses its built-in [PostgreSQL](#) database for data storage. In addition, Strapi allows to create a REST API, which is used to fetch and manage data on the front end, ensuring smooth and efficient interaction between the application's backend and frontend.

5.2.4 User Manual Development

In response to the workshop discussions and survey findings, a comprehensive NSM manual that provides detailed guidance on every aspect of the platform was developed and shared with all city partners. The manual includes terminology definitions to clarify distinctions between stories, homepages, threads, and resources. It also offers step-by-step instructions for creating and editing content including homepage layouts, story formats, and thread creation as well as integrating multimedia content, embedding maps, managing user roles through the city dashboard etc.

The manual also offers storytelling best practices, including tips on narrative structure, emotional engagement, and scrollytelling techniques. Cities can use these guidelines to craft compelling, locally relevant stories that combine personal testimony with data-driven insights.

Importantly, the manual supports city-level governance by outlining backend functionalities such as user role management, content editing, and request handling. These features ensure that each city can independently oversee its NSM presence while contributing to the broader UP2030 narrative.

The manual is designed to evolve with the platform. Future updates may include additional examples, Frequently Asked Questions (FAQs), and city-specific case studies based on ongoing feedback.

5.2.5 Privacy and Ethics Compliance

After the GenA workshop, it became clear that the platform needed proper legal documentation to ensure compliance and protect both the project and its users. For this reason, a meeting was arranged with the Law and Internet Foundation (LIF), the legal partner of UP2030, to discuss the required steps. The conclusion was that two documents had to be prepared: a Privacy Policy and a set of Terms & Conditions.

LIF advised on the key points these documents should cover and shared relevant material from previous deliverables to help clarify the necessary legal restrictions. A follow-up meeting took place

with CERTH's legal team, where the tool was presented, its functionality was explained, and detailed questions were answered to ensure the documents would accurately reflect the platform's behavior.

Based on this input, CERTH's legal team prepared the first draft of both documents. LIF then reviewed the draft, provided feedback, and after the necessary adjustments were made, the documents were approved. The final versions were integrated into the platform and are now presented to users during the registration process.

6 Upscaling and Validation Phase: Refinement, Testing, and Dissemination

The upscaling phase of UP2030 was designed to build on the prototypes developed during the action phase by enabling the transition from experimentation to implementation. This phase focused on the creation of scalable and inclusive strategies for achieving climate neutrality, with a particular focus on strengthening local governance frameworks, deepening citizen engagement, and preparing cities for long-term outreach and impact. As part of this effort, cities collaboratively refined their NSMs through a series of workshops and participatory sessions. These activities ensured that the platform could effectively support context-sensitive storytelling and climate communication, tailored to the lived experiences and priorities of diverse urban communities, ahead of its public launch.

6.1 Feedback Workshops

During the upscaling phase, three key workshops were held to support the development and refinement of the NSMs within the UP2030 project. These sessions, held on April 3, September 10, and September 12, 2025, brought together representatives from pilot cities to collaboratively reflect on their NSM drafts, share challenges, and receive structured feedback from peers and the VUB and CERTH teams.

The NSMs are a central component of the UP2030 citizen engagement strategy, designed to communicate each city's journey toward climate neutrality in an accessible, engaging, and locally grounded way. The workshops were structured to align with the broader project timeline: cities were expected to produce a first draft of their NSMs by the end of the action phase (February 2025) and refine them during the upscale phase in preparation for public launch.

Each workshop followed a consistent structure: a brief walkthrough of the platform's features and recent updates, followed by city presentations, peer feedback, and technical guidance. The sessions also served as a space for cities to exchange strategies, troubleshoot common challenges, and align their storytelling efforts with the broader goals of the UP2030 project.

6.1.1 Workshop Participation Overview

April 3, 2025 – First Feedback Round

- Participating cities: Belfast, Granollers, Budapest
- Focus: Initial feedback on NSM drafts, platform walkthrough, and peer exchange.
- Highlights:
 - Belfast introduced its persona-based storytelling approach, developed through extensive citizen workshops. The city shared early visual and narrative concepts aimed at making climate neutrality relatable to diverse community profiles.
 - Granollers presented its co-creation process and strategic framing, emphasizing how the NSM could document participatory planning and align with broader municipal goals.
 - Budapest discussed conceptual challenges in adapting the Healthy Streets methodology to the NSM format, particularly given its city-wide scope and dual audience of planners and citizens.

September 10, 2025 – Final Refinement Workshop I

- Participating cities: Milan, Belfast, Budapest, Rotterdam
- Focus: Final feedback, integration strategies, and outreach planning.

- Highlights:
 - Milan showcased a visually rich NSM focused on the ecological value of green spaces, urban cooling, and carbon sequestration. The city also discussed political sensitivities around data sharing and the need for strategic communication.
 - Belfast presented updates to its persona-driven NSM, including AI-generated illustrations and interactive storytelling elements. The city emphasized emotional resonance and behavioral change as key goals.
 - Budapest shared progress on visual storytelling and clarified its dual-purpose strategy: targeting district-level planners while also engaging citizens through relatable urban transformations.
 - Rotterdam outlined plans for a virtual tour of the Bospolder-Tussendijken (BoTu) neighborhood, using the platform's mapping features to simulate a walk-through experience and highlight citizen-led initiatives.

September 12, 2025 – Final Refinement Workshop II

- Participating cities: Lisbon, Thessaloniki, Granollers, Istanbul, Muenster
- Observer: Zagreb
- Focus: Final feedback, integration strategies, and outreach planning.
- Highlights:
 - Lisbon presented a comprehensive NSM featuring video interviews with stakeholders, documentation of pilot sites, and alignment with the city's climate contract. The map was structured around four pilot locations and included real citizen voices.
 - Thessaloniki shared a structured narrative that moved from challenges to vision, integrating adaptive pathways and visualizations of future urban scenarios. The NSM was closely tied to the city's participatory workshops and strategic planning.
 - Granollers emphasized strategic alignment and dynamic data integration, using interactive maps and external links to municipal platforms to ensure long-term relevance and updateability.
 - Istanbul showcased solar energy modelling and PV-integrated urban furniture, blending technical outputs with imaginative storytelling to make energy transition more tangible.
 - Muenster focused on compact neighborhoods and climate adaptation, using data visualizations and open data links to encourage citizen engagement and informed decision-making.
 - Zagreb attended as an observer to learn from peer cities and explore future engagement with the platform, particularly in relation to citizen storytelling and digital climate communication.

6.1.2 [Key Themes and Insights](#)

Each workshop began with a walkthrough of the platform's features, including new functionalities such as interactive map layers, thread creation for citizen stories, and resource pages for supplementary content. These features were introduced to help city's better structure their narratives, visualize pilot areas, and potentially crowdsource stories from citizens in the future.

City presentations revealed diverse storytelling strategies shaped by local contexts. Belfast's personas, Milan's ecological framing, Budapest's planning-oriented approach, and Thessaloniki's adaptive pathways all demonstrated how NSMs could be tailored to different audiences and goals. Lisbon and Granollers emphasized stakeholder engagement and institutional alignment, while Istanbul and Muenster explored technical modelling and data-driven storytelling.

Common challenges included:

- Balancing technical depth with accessibility
- Ensuring visual coherence and narrative clarity
- Navigating political sensitivities around data sharing
- Structuring content to maintain reader engagement

Cities were encouraged to reduce text density, highlight key messages through formatting and color, and make better use of the platform's interactive features. Ending with a clear call to action, whether linking to municipal resources, inviting citizen participation, or promoting behavioral change, was repeatedly emphasized.

6.1.3 [Next Steps](#)

Cities finalized their NSMs by October 2025, ahead of the platform's public launch. Outreach efforts will follow, with cities promoting their maps through municipal channels, and UP2030 amplifying visibility via its website and social media. The platform will remain active for at least five years, offering cities a long-term tool for engagement, storytelling, and strategic planning.

Overall, the NSM workshops fostered a collaborative environment for peer learning, technical support, and creative exchange. They helped cities transform complex urban interventions into compelling digital narratives, reinforcing the UP2030 project's commitment to inclusive, participatory, and locally resonant climate action.

6.2 [Testing and Validation with Students](#)

To ensure the NSM platform is responsive to the needs and aspirations of younger generations, who are among the most vulnerable to the long-term impacts of climate change (Clayton, 2020), a dedicated testing and validation workshop was conducted with students during the 2025 [TU Delft Summer School](#) on Climate, Cities and Design, and facilitated by the TU Delft team.

The workshop, led by Dr. Cora Van Leeuwen (VUB), took place in person at TU Delft in the Netherlands and involved 65 students from over 45 countries. Participants ranged from bachelor's to PhD level, primarily from disciplines such as architecture, urban planning, and the social sciences with a predominance of architecture students. All participants provided informed consent via Qualtrics (see informed consent form in Annex 2: Informed Consent Form).

6.2.1 [Workshop Structure](#)

The two-hour session (10:30–12:30) was structured as follows:

1. Introduction: Presentation of the NSM platform concept, the digital storytelling methodology using maps, and an overview of the UP2030 project and its goals.
2. Platform Walkthrough: Demonstration of the platform's main features and workflow.
3. Onboarding: Participants signed up via Qualtrics and received access to the platform.
4. Story Creation & Evaluation: In pairs or small groups, students created short stories using the platform while evaluating its strengths and limitations. Feedback was provided in real-time using post-its on a shared Miro board.

5. Plenary Reflection: A group discussion focused on accessibility, storytelling potential, usability, and functionality.
6. Conclusion: Final reflections and discussion of next steps for platform development.

Figure 39: Participants Testing NSM in TU Delft’s Summer School

6.2.2 Summary of Student Feedback

The table below summarizes the key insights gathered from student participants, organized by category:

Table 2: Summary of student feedback from TU Delft Summer School workshop

Category	Positive Aspects	Challenges Faced	Requested Improvements
Storytelling & Content	Collaborative Storytelling concept Ability to react to others’ experiences	Confusing distinction between pages and stories Lack of thematic orientation	Add titles and descriptions Hashtags or keywords for categorization Climate related storytelling categories Pins should reflect sentiment or theme
User Interface	User-friendly editing interface Visual simplicity of the map	Overwhelming design options No clear guidance for first time users	Step-by-step tutorial Emoji reactions Post-editing options

Map & Geolocation	Geolocated stories viewable on map	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Pins are not clickable Location tags not linked to content Misaligned auto-location No connection between location tags and story content 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Clickable pins with pop-ups Satellite/street view Search and zoom features
Media & Flexibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Multiple media sections Customizable symbology 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Only one image per story page Required media upload even for text-only stories 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Upload videos via link Add multiple images Clarify allowed image types
Accessibility	Multilingual support	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Language mismatch Difficult for older adults/non-tech-savvy users 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mobile optimization Simplified layout for broader accessibility
Performance		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> App slowed down with many users Website failed to load 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improve responsiveness and scalability
Collaboration & AI			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Real-time collaboration features (similar to Miro) AI image generator for story visualization

The feedback collected during the TU Delft Summer School workshop was integrated into the next development phase of the NSM platform by CERTH ahead of its public launch. Several of the suggested improvements, such as enhanced map interaction and media flexibility, were already part of the planned roadmap. Others, including AI integration for story visualization, go beyond the scope of the current deliverable but have been noted for future consideration. This iterative, user-driven approach ensures that the platform evolves in alignment with the expectations and needs of its most climate-vulnerable users.

6.3 [Tutorial Videos for MOOC](#)

As part of the UP2030 training program “*How to Build Carbon Neutral, Resilient and Just Cities*”, VUB and CERTH contributed three tutorial videos to support the MOOC. The program is designed to equip city practitioners with the knowledge and tools needed to integrate climate neutrality, resilience and social justice into urban planning, using the 5UPs framework: UP-Dating, UP-Skilling, UP-Grading, UP-Scaling, and UP-Taking.

The videos produced by VUB and CERTH focus on the NSM platform and include:

1. Introduction to NSM - An overview of the platform’s purpose and role within UP2030.
2. Step-by-Step Tutorial - A guided walkthrough on how to create a digital story using the NSM tool.

3. Application in Belfast - A case study demonstrating how the NSM was used in Belfast to engage citizens through persona-based storytelling.

These videos will be available and integrated into the MOOC curriculum after the project ends and made accessible as standalone resources for learners with specific interests in digital storytelling and citizen engagement.

6.4 Outreach to Other Cities

6.4.1 CLIMABOROUGH

At the start of the project's final year (January 2025, M25), the UP2030 coordination team informed the project's tool providers about a call for tender organized by the sister project [CLIMABOROUGH](#). The tender aimed to propose socio-technical solutions addressing the specific challenges defined by the five participating cities.

The VUB and CERTH first reviewed the challenges and needs of the five cities described on the project's website. Among them, Sofia's case stood out as the most relevant for a solution like NSM, with some additions to the existing tool, followed by Issy-les-Moulineaux.

Five Preliminary Market Consultations were organized, one for each city. During these sessions, each city presented its challenge, and the organizers outlined the overall process of the tender. After attending all the sessions, the initial assessment was confirmed, and the focus shifted to the two cities whose challenges best aligned with the NSM approach: Sofia and Issy-les-Moulineaux.

Sofia's challenge focused on developing a digital platform to raise awareness and engage citizens in sustainable waste management. The goal was to inform residents about recycling options, support issue reporting, and promote responsible waste practices in line with the city's circular economy objectives.

Issy-les-Moulineaux's challenge aimed to expand citizen participation in its zero-carbon initiative, using data-driven solutions to scale activities, sustain engagement, and introduce an inter-city challenge to encourage wider involvement in climate action.

At the beginning of February (M26), the Solution Proposal Description Form was submitted. This document briefly described the proposed solution and included the required information. The submission was made by VUB and CDXi, a CERTH spin-off that exploits and commercializes the organization's research results.

At the beginning of April (M28), the call for tender entered the qualification phase, during which all economic operators could submit information about their legal status, finances, and personnel. For Issy-les-Moulineaux, the required documents could not be collected and submitted on time due to procedural delays in the administrative approval process.

After passing the qualification phase for Sofia, the next step (M31) required the submission of a detailed technical offer. This included a description of the tool, a time plan, and an explanation of how the proposed application would meet the city's minimum requirements.

The next phase involved a meeting with representatives from Sofia Municipality and a responsible officer from the CLIMABOROUGH project. During this meeting, the proposed solution was presented, its alignment with the minimum requirements was confirmed, and feedback was received on how it could be adapted further to better address the city's needs. Following this meeting, a new deadline was set for submitting the final technical offer, along with the financial proposal (M34).

Now, the next and final phase includes the selection of the tools that will be implemented in each city. The solution proposed to Sofia Municipality builds upon NSM, incorporating its existing features such as Stories, Threads, and Resources, while adding new ones: Reports, an AI chatbot for answering waste

management queries, an interactive map of recycling points, a management dashboard, analytics, and gamification elements to enhance user engagement.

6.4.2 Re-Value

As part of UP2030's broader dissemination and cross-project collaboration efforts, the NSM platform was presented at the [Re-Value](#) Rounds webinar on January 29, 2025, hosted by the city of Pisek and coordinated by ICLEI. The session, titled "Engage, Educate, Empower: Digital Approaches for Climate Action", focused on citizen engagement, digital communication, and the integration of IT tools in urban transformation processes.

Although the Re-Value Rounds were primarily designed for cities participating in the Re-Value project, VUB and CERTH were invited to contribute due to the thematic relevance of the NSM platform. The invitation was extended to the UP2030 coordination team who forwarded it to the NSM team after recognizing the potential of the NSM platform to complement the session's focus on citizen engagement and digital storytelling.

Milutin Djuraskovic (VUB) and Nick Pantelidis (CERTH) delivered a presentation titled: "Neutrality Story Maps: Leveraging Digital Storytelling for Citizen Engagement".

The presentation introduced the NSM platform's core features, its role within UP2030's citizen engagement strategy, and showcased examples from participating cities such as Belfast, Milan, and Thessaloniki. The session emphasized how digital storytelling can help cities communicate complex climate neutrality goals in a locally grounded and emotionally resonant way. The presentation recording can be found on this [link](#).

Other contributors included:

- Miloš Prokýšek (Smart Pisek), who presented on the evolution of Pisek's digital engagement strategy.
- Jasper De Jonge (City of Tampere), representing the WeGenerate project, who spoke about Digital Twins for inclusive urban futures.

The webinar attracted interest from several cities, particularly regarding the NSM platform's potential for participatory storytelling and citizen-led climate narratives. Following the session, VUB and CERTH reached out to interested municipalities to explore the possibility of organizing a hands-on workshop to test the platform with their citizens, however scheduling constraints prevented the workshop from taking place.

This external engagement reinforced the relevance of the NSM platform beyond the UP2030 consortium and highlighted its adaptability to different urban contexts and citizen engagement strategies.

7 Public Launch of Neutrality Story Maps

The NSM platform was officially launched to the public on October 20, 2025, marking a significant milestone in the UP2030 project's commitment to inclusive climate storytelling. Developed through a co-design process with ten pilot cities, NSM enables citizens to map their everyday experiences of climate change and urban transformation, linking personal narratives to specific places.

To promote the launch, a coordinated outreach campaign was carried out across multiple channels:

- A dedicated blog post was published on the UP2030 website, introducing the platform and its purpose: [Neutrality Story Maps Goes Public: Mapping Everyday Climate Experiences](#).
- The launch was featured in the UP2030 newsletter, reaching stakeholders across Europe.
- Each pilot city promoted the platform on their official websites and communication channels, tailoring the message to local audiences and priorities.
- The VUB amplified the launch through its institutional channels, including social media and internal networks.

The platform is accessible at: <https://m4d.services.itl.gr/up2030/app/>, where users can explore city-specific pages, contribute stories, and engage with multimedia narratives.

This public launch marks the beginning of NSM's integration into local engagement strategies, supporting cities in fostering dialogue, transparency, and citizen participation in the journey toward climate neutrality.

8 Analysis of Final NSMs and Behavior Change Potential

This section reviews the final NSMs developed by the UP2030 pilot cities and assesses their potential to support climate-conscious behavior. It distinguishes between homepages, which usually communicate strategic goals and diagnose local climate challenges, and stories pages, which convey lived experiences, place-based narratives, and examples of climate action. Together, these components show how cities translate their climate priorities into narrative, spatial, and visual communication to frame challenges, engage residents, and motivate sustainable practices. The analysis follows the project's two working groups: Group 1 cities, which primarily focused on knowledge development, training programs, and planning instruments; and Group 2 cities, which centered their efforts on technical assessments and on-the-ground interventions. It examines how NSMs may act as drivers of behavior change via emotional resonance, social learning, accessible information, and visibility of practical, replicable actions (Ajzen, 1991; Abrahamse & Steg, 2013; Clayton, 2020; Moser & Dilling, 2011; Steg & De Groot, 2019; Veland et al., 2018).

8.1 Group 1 Cities

8.1.1 Homepage vs. Stories Page

Across Group 1, homepages typically provide an overview of local climate ambitions, priority themes (e.g. greening, mobility, retrofit, resilience), and the environmental and social pressures shaping specific neighborhoods. They frequently combine high-level goals such as emission-reduction or resilience targets with concise explanations of local risks like heat stress, flooding, poor air quality, congestion, or socio-economic inequalities. Maps and diagnostics (e.g. heat, noise, flooding, or cycling-potential maps) are often used to justify why interventions are needed, in line with evidence that clear causal explanations help people understand the links between everyday environments and climate risks (Santamouris, 2014; Steg & De Groot, 2019).

Where stories pages exist, they usually translate these strategic narratives into more concrete, recognizable situations: everyday journeys, streets, squares, schools, or community spaces. One NSM focuses on persona-based storytelling, using composite characters built from interviews and workshops; others foreground specific projects such as community gardens, "healthy streets" interventions, or resilience initiatives. A few cities instead use a single scrollytelling homepage rather than a separate stories page, embedding narrative elements along a linear "climate journey".

Overall, the division between homepages and stories pages works well conceptually: homepages set the scene and clarify "why change is needed", while stories pages illustrate "how change is lived" in specific places. However, the separation is not always fully exploited. In several NSMs, the homepage already carries dense narrative content, while the stories page remains underused or absent, limiting the depth of experiential material that citizens can explore.

8.1.2 Content Characteristics

Content across Group 1 NSMs tends to sit on a spectrum between technically oriented communication and lived-experience storytelling. On the more experiential end, some maps emphasize daily routines, pressures, and trade-offs such as balancing care responsibilities with commuting, coping with rising bills, or adjusting to changing weather patterns. These narratives frame climate action as incremental adjustments rather than radical lifestyle changes, which aligns with evidence that small, feasible steps are more likely to be adopted and maintained (Moser & Dilling, 2011; Wilson et al., 2015).

On the more institutional end, other NSMs lean heavily on data, diagnostics, and policy language. They effectively communicate the rationale for interventions but provide fewer first-person accounts or micro-stories about how residents understand and navigate climate challenges. This reduces

emotional depth and limits opportunities for identification, even when analytical clarity is strong (Clayton, 2020).

Most NSMs succeed in making climate issues legible and place-based. Streets, squares, riverfronts, or historic districts are presented as concrete settings where climate neutrality, livability, and justice intersect. Yet representation remains uneven. Some NSMs primarily feature institutional voices or already-active groups, while perspectives from migrants, renters, people with disabilities, youth, or small businesses are less visible. This is a critical gap, given research showing that participatory and narrative methods are particularly valuable for surfacing distributive, procedural, and recognitional injustices that standard planning tools overlook (de Jager et al., 2017; Veland et al., 2018).

8.1.3 Behavior Change Potential

Taken together, Group 1 NSMs exhibit several mechanisms with clear potential to support behavior change. The main pathways are:

1. **Emotional resonance and identity.** Persona-based or resident-led stories allow users to recognize elements of their own lives in the narratives like busy families, worried students, older residents, volunteers, or entrepreneurs. Perceived similarity and social identity processes are known to strengthen openness to new practices and intentions (Ajzen, 1991; Clayton, 2020). Where NSMs emphasize co-benefits such as better health, lower bills, safer streets, and less stress, the framing aligns with evidence that such outcomes often motivate pro-environmental action more effectively than abstract carbon metrics (Steg & De Groot, 2019).
2. **Social learning and normative modelling.** Several NSMs present concrete models of desired behavior and street use such as walking, cycling, using greener public spaces, participating in community gardens, joining energy cooperatives, or attending climate-related workshops. These examples function as social models and help establish “what people like me do”, supporting descriptive and injunctive norms (Bandura, 1977; Abrahamse & Steg, 2013; Bollinger & Gillingham, 2012).
3. **Perceived control and understanding.** By linking maps and diagnostics to specific interventions, NSMs can enhance users’ sense of efficacy: they show how sealed surfaces, tree cover, or mobility choices shape local comfort and risk, and how practices such as supporting green roofs, retrofits, or active mobility contribute to city-wide goals. Perceived behavioral control and understanding of causal mechanisms are central determinants of climate-relevant intentions (Ajzen, 1991; Moser & Dilling, 2011).
4. **Participation architectures and pathways to action.** Some NSMs explicitly connect communication with governance tools such as training programs, climate contracts, participation portals, or calls for co-design. These provide concrete routes from awareness to action, consistent with research showing that ongoing, structured opportunities for involvement are crucial for sustained engagement (Reed, 2008; Adelle et al., 2022).

At the same time, these mechanisms are often only partially realized. In many NSMs, behavior-change pathways remain implicit: the user is shown what has changed or what others are doing but receives limited guidance on “what you can do next”, where to sign up, or how to access support. Without explicit action prompts, the leap from inspiration to practice is likely to remain fragile (Moser & Dilling, 2011).

8.1.4 Limitations

Across Group 1 NSMs, several recurrent limitations can reduce behavior-change potential:

- **Limited interactivity and bottom-up contribution.** Many platforms currently operate as curated showcases with restricted opportunities for citizens to upload stories, comment, or interact. Where interactive features exist, they are sometimes disabled for moderation

reasons. This constrains peer-to-peer learning, co-production of knowledge, and the evolution of social norms, despite evidence that deliberative and participatory processes can strengthen commitment and legitimacy (Abrahamse & Steg, 2013; Reed, 2008).

- **Narrow range of voices.** Despite ambitions around inclusivity, the number of stories is often small, and certain groups (e.g. migrants, low-income residents, youth, people with disabilities, informal workers, local businesses) remain under-represented. These risks reinforcing existing patterns of “invited participation” rather than genuinely broadening who gets to narrate climate futures (de Jager et al., 2017).
- **Lack of narrative conflict.** Many stories emphasize successful projects and positive outcomes while downplaying conflicts, trade-offs, or failures (for example, tensions around reallocating parking, fears about safety, or affordability constraints). Research in climate communication suggests that overly polished narratives can undermine perceived authenticity and make transitions appear smoother than they are, reducing trust and learning opportunities (Moser & Dilling, 2011; Pezzullo & Cox, 2025).
- **Unclear linkage to structural conditions.** While NSMs often mention local challenges, they rarely unpack how socio-economic inequality, housing precarity, or governance constraints shape residents’ ability to sustain new practices. Without acknowledging these conditions, recommended actions may feel aspirational or inaccessible to more vulnerable groups (Pelling, 2010; Amorim-Maia et al., 2022).
- **Digital divide and capacity demands.** The effectiveness of NSMs depends on digital skills, language, and access to devices. Moderation, translation, and content curation also require staff time, which some municipalities currently lack. These institutional constraints risk limiting the frequency and diversity of updates, with implications for long-term engagement.

Given these limitations, it is important to interpret NSMs as promising but still experimental tools for behavior change. Robust evaluation and longitudinal research are needed to substantiate their actual effects on practices and norms.

8.1.5 Conclusion

In aggregate, Group 1 NSMs provide a rich testbed for understanding how digital storytelling and mapping can support climate-neutral, socially just urban transformations. Homepages tend to excel at clarifying local challenges and strategic responses, while stories pages where developed humanize these strategies through persona-based and place-based narratives. Together, they make climate neutrality more tangible by connecting city-level commitments to everyday experiences, co-benefits, and local identities.

To fully realize their potential to trigger behavior change, future iterations could:

1. broaden the range of storytellers and perspectives, particularly from structurally disadvantaged groups;
2. add low-threshold participation options such as comments and clear calls to action linked to local programs;
3. be more transparent about conflicts, trade-offs, and learning processes; and
4. more explicitly connect narrative content to structural supports (funding schemes, legal changes, services) that make sustainable practices feasible.

These enhancements would align NSMs more closely with evidence on social learning, participatory governance, and environmental behavior change, and help them evolve from attractive communication tools into more powerful catalysts for climate-conscious, justice-oriented urban living.

8.2 [Group 2 Cities](#)

8.2.1 [Homepage vs. Stories Page](#)

Across Group 2, NSMs typically present cities as testing grounds for climate neutrality, where technical pilots, public facilities, and neighborhood interventions are used to demonstrate what low-carbon, climate-resilient living can look like in practice. Homepages usually set out the overarching ambitions (e.g. resilience, inclusion, climate neutrality) and then introduce a portfolio of pilots: retrofitted buildings, public spaces redesigned with nature-based solutions, school or market interventions, and demonstration objects for clean energy or cooling. These pages often link local work to wider frameworks, such as adaptive pathways, resilience assessment tools, or mission-oriented KPIs, signaling that pilots are embedded in strategic planning (Haasnoot et al., 2013; Turnhout et al., 2020).

Where a stories page exists, it tends to zoom in on specific sites: a school, market, library, sports club, park, or research campus and describe concrete changes: solar self-consumption schemes, rainwater management, facade greening, circularity initiatives, or educational experiments. Some NSMs use resident testimonials or short quotes from local coordinators, while others rely on descriptive, institutional narratives or case-study style write-ups. A few cities merge these elements into a single scrollytelling page rather than clearly separating “homepage” and “stories” functions.

Overall, the structure creates a clear movement from city-scale challenge (heat, flooding, emissions, food resilience) to place-based projects. However, the degree to which stories pages provide rich, everyday narratives as opposed to technical descriptions of pilots varies considerably.

8.2.2 [Content Characteristics](#)

The content of Group 2 NSMs is generally more technical and implementation-oriented than in Group 1. Several maps foreground tools, indicators, and methods: resilience assessment frameworks, climate-shelter networks, monitoring of air and noise pollution, carbon and participation KPIs, or explanations of urban heat island and carbon sequestration processes. This gives users a strong sense that actions are measurable, evidence-based, and connected to climate science (Emilsson & Ode Sang, 2017; Santamouris, 2014).

At the same time, many NSMs work to humanize these technical elements. Some use historical narrative (e.g. past floods, food traditions, or changing land-use patterns) to frame today’s climate challenges, building emotional connections and place attachment (Clayton, 2020; Scannell & Gifford, 2010). Others rely on short quotes from facility coordinators or residents, or on school-based experiments that invite pupils and teachers into hands-on learning. Public facilities like libraries, markets, sports clubs, research campuses and parks serve as key narrative anchors where mitigation, adaptation, and social inclusion intersect.

However, resident voices remain relatively thin. In many cases, institutions speak on behalf of communities since stories emphasize what has been implemented and measured, rather than how different social groups experience these changes in daily life. This limits the exploration of distributive and recognitional dimensions of justice, even where resilience and inclusion are central goals (Anguelovski et al., 2019).

8.2.3 [Behavior Change Potential](#)

Group 2 NSMs display several promising mechanisms for supporting climate-conscious behavior:

1. **Demonstration through pilots and public facilities.** By situating interventions in familiar venues, NSMs show how climate action can be woven into everyday routines: using shaded routes, engaging with nature-based cooling, participating in circularity schemes, or experiencing solar self-consumption on site. Such visible, trusted settings support social learning and norm formation, particularly when accompanied by simple performance indicators (Abrahamse & Steg, 2013; Bouman et al., 2021).

2. **Framing co-benefits and personal relevance.** Many NSMs emphasize reduced energy bills, improved thermal comfort, quieter streets, better food quality, or more pleasant public spaces as key benefits. Research consistently finds that such co-benefits can be more motivating than abstract emissions reductions (Wilson et al., 2015; Bouman et al., 2021).
3. **Building capabilities and self-efficacy.** Educational pilots such as school-based experiments, climate walks, or participatory “future newspaper” exercises, encourage users to test low-impact practices, interpret indicators, and understand causal links between actions and outcomes. This can strengthen perceived behavioral control and climate efficacy, central determinants in the theory of planned behavior (Ajzen, 1991; Bouman et al., 2021).
4. **Anchoring local action in broader governance frameworks.** The use of adaptive pathways, resilience tools, and KPI dashboards (even if not yet fully public-facing) signals that individual and local actions are part of a larger citywide transition. When residents see that small interventions connect to mission targets and monitoring frameworks, their efforts are more likely to feel meaningful and consequential (Turnhout et al., 2020; Moser & Dilling, 2011).

Yet in many NSMs, these pathways stop at awareness and inspiration. Explicit micro-level prompts highlighting “what you can do at home, this week”, and easy-to-find information on incentives, support programs, or participation channels are often missing. This weakens the critical bridge from intention to sustained behavior (Moser & Dilling, 2011).

8.2.4 Limitations

Across Group 2 NSMs, several recurring limitations can constrain behavior change potential:

- **One-way communication and limited interactivity.** Most platforms operate as curated showcases of pilots and methods. Opportunities for users to upload their own stories, comment on projects, or access live dashboards are scarce. This limits peer-to-peer learning, co-production, and continuous feedback, even though such features are known to strengthen commitment and collective efficacy over time (Abrahamse & Steg, 2013; Reed, 2008).
- **Unequal treatment of spatial justice.** While some NSMs reference vulnerability indicators, climate shelters, or treeless and overheated areas, equity concerns are rarely visualized systematically through maps of exposure, access to green space, or food and energy security. Without this, it is difficult for residents to locate themselves within the transition or for cities to publicly justify why certain neighborhoods or groups are prioritized (Anguelovski et al., 2019).
- **Narrow participation base.** Engagement activities often focus on schools, organized civil-society groups, or facility managers. Other constituencies like renters, low-income households, migrants, small businesses, or older adults outside formal organizations appear less visibly. These risks reproducing familiar participation biases, with more empowered actors more likely to be represented (Anguelovski et al., 2019).
- **Restricted feedback on progress and impact.** Even where monitoring tools and KPIs exist, they are not always translated into accessible, public-facing indicators (e.g. number of retrofitted buildings, energy saved, comfort gains, or participation figures). Without visible trajectories of change, it is harder for individuals to see how their actions aggregate, weakening motivation and shared ownership (Abrahamse & Steg, 2013; Moser & Dilling, 2011).

Given these constraints, behavior change remains theoretically grounded rather than empirically demonstrated, and systematic evaluation of actual behavioral impacts should be a priority for future work.

8.2.5 Conclusion

Overall, Group 2 NSMs provide a strong and diverse portfolio of implementation-oriented story maps. They excel at making climate neutrality tangible through concrete pilots, public facilities, and technical tools, and they integrate scientific explanation, monitoring, and co-benefits in ways that can meaningfully influence awareness, perceived efficacy, and norms.

To enhance their behavioral impact and alignment with just-transition principles, future iterations could:

1. pair technical and institutional narratives with more first-person stories from diverse residents;
2. provide simple, recurring prompts for household and community-level actions, linked directly to local support schemes and incentives;
3. make equity dimensions visible through spatialized indicators of vulnerability, access, and benefits; and
4. open up monitoring systems so that residents can track progress and see how small experiments and pilots contribute to citywide goals.

Such developments would better connect knowledge, participation, and justice, helping Group 2 NSMs evolve from exemplary project portfolios into robust, participatory infrastructures for long-term climate-conscious behavior in everyday urban life.

9 Reflections and Conclusions

9.1 Challenges of Co-Design and Lessons Learned

The co-design of the NSM platform brought together ten cities with diverse priorities, capacities, and expectations. This diversity enriched the process but also created uneven levels of participation. While some cities saw the tool as an opportunity to communicate climate action and were eager to shape it, others struggled to integrate it into their local engagement strategies. Tight schedules, limited staff, political changes, and digital literacy gaps often hindered consistent involvement. These constraints meant that, in some cases, workshops remained superficial, citizen participation was limited, and follow-up activities were difficult to sustain.

Although NSM was initially envisioned as a participatory platform for citizen-led climate storytelling, the co-design process gradually shifted its trajectory. In early discussions, several cities expressed openness to a two-way model where residents and city representatives could upload stories. However, as the process evolved, many preferred a more controlled approach, using the tool mainly to highlight municipal initiatives. This was particularly evident in the Cities Knowledge Exchange Event in Rotterdam (see section 2.2.3 in [D6.6 - Neutrality Story Maps for Pilot Cities 1](#)), where city representatives described three possible uses for the tool: a crowdsourcing platform for citizen stories; a curated map of municipal success stories; or a narrative data-based webpage created jointly with the project team. Most cities ultimately selected the second or third option. As a result, the NSM platform became more of an institutional storytelling platform than a space for citizen co-authorship.

This shift also reflected broader dynamics in the co-design process. While the tool was developed with all pilot cities, the process leaned more toward consultation than full co-creation. Due to recruitment challenges and limited time, early workshops primarily involved municipal staff or pre-existing advisory groups rather than diverse citizen voices. Key design decisions, for example, removing the possibility to comment on stories, were made without direct citizen feedback, despite early interest in more interactive features. This imbalance limited the range of perspectives embedded in the tool and constrained its ability to serve as a genuinely participatory instrument.

Yet, the process still generated important forms of knowledge exchange. Workshops and cross-city meetings allowed municipal teams, technical partners, and researchers to compare approaches and reflect on how digital storytelling could support climate communication. Cities learned from each other's methods: Belfast's use of personas, Rotterdam's emphasis on resilience and community assets, Budapest's use of storytelling to reframe public space and health, Thessaloniki's intergenerational engagement activities, or Lisbon's integration of indicators and facility-based pilots. These exchanges helped build a shared understanding of how narrative tools can support climate neutrality when adapted to different institutional cultures.

Despite the challenges, the co-design process produced several positive outcomes. It heightened awareness of the importance of narrative in climate action, encouraged stronger collaboration between municipal departments and research partners, and helped cities experiment with new digital engagement formats. In the cities of Thessaloniki, Lisbon, or Zagreb, the process strengthened ongoing participation efforts by giving visibility to local voices, community workshops, or school-based experiments. In the other cities, the discussions prompted reflections on future citizen involvement and on how communication tools could better support long-term climate strategies.

Overall, the NSM co-design process illustrates both the value and the difficulty of building participatory digital tools in multi-stakeholder urban projects. It showed that meaningful co-creation requires time, continuity, and institutional commitment. While the final tool leaned more toward institutional communication than originally planned, the process itself offered valuable lessons about participation, collaboration, and the need to balance flexibility with local realities. These insights can inform future efforts that aim to combine digital storytelling, climate action, and genuine citizen engagement.

9.2 Conclusion

The development of the NSM platform constitutes a key achievement of the UP2030 project in supporting cities on their pathways toward climate neutrality. Across the co-design cycles conducted with the ten pilot cities, the platform evolved from an initial concept into a functional, publicly accessible tool that enables cities to communicate climate challenges, showcase local initiatives, and engage residents through place-based storytelling and mapped narratives.

Over the course of the second co-design phase, cities moved from exploration to active implementation. They created stories, tested layouts, refined content structures, and integrated local datasets. This phase revealed substantial variation across pilot contexts: while some cities invested heavily in shaping the platform, others faced internal constraints that resulted in more limited engagement. These differing capacities and strategic priorities shaped the final design, which had to remain flexible and accommodate a range of use cases. Despite this unevenness, the co-design activities resulted in valuable knowledge exchange between municipalities, technical partners, and researchers. Cities shared communication practices, learned from one another's approaches, and gained a clearer understanding of how digital storytelling can support climate governance. The involvement of students and external stakeholders further broadened the learning environment and reinforced the platform's applicability beyond the project consortium.

The platform itself has matured significantly. NSM now offers a stable and user-friendly environment that supports multimedia storytelling, scrollytelling homepages, geolocated narratives, and integrated maps. Key improvements were directly informed by co-design feedback and have strengthened the platform's usability and relevance for cities. With its public launch, NSM has transitioned from TRL 2 to TRL 7, achieving a transition from initial feasibility to operational readiness.

Several lessons emerged throughout the process. First, effective co-design requires sustained engagement, internal coordination, and sufficient capacity at city level. Second, cities differ in how they approach digital storytelling: some emphasize broad citizen engagement, while others focus on institutional communication. The final platform reflects these varied expectations through a hybrid design that supports both approaches. Third, NSM demonstrates that narrative communication can play an important role in making climate neutrality more tangible by highlighting concrete examples, local pathways, and recognizable places.

The process also exposed limitations. Early-stage citizen involvement remained limited, and the platform shifted over time from participatory storytelling toward more curated, city-led communication. This reflects broader structural challenges in large-scale projects, including tight timelines, competing municipal priorities, and constraints related to staffing and resources. Addressing these challenges in future iterations, particularly by strengthening participation mechanisms and diversifying story contributors, will be essential to unlocking the platform's full potential.

Overall, NSM provides cities with a flexible, replicable, and visually compelling tool for communicating climate challenges and actions at the neighborhood and city scale. Its long-term impact will depend on continued content development, integration into municipal workflows, and future enhancements that strengthen citizen participation, spatial justice perspectives, and progress-tracking features. The experience gained through UP2030 offers a solid foundation for further development and provides valuable insights for future European initiatives seeking to combine digital tools, participatory approaches, digital storytelling using maps in support of climate-neutral urban transitions.

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10 Annex

Annex 1: Requirements List

ID	Requirement	Priority
1	Users	
1.1	Registration to the platform	Must
1.2	Provide proof that they live in the city	Won't
1.3	Provide information such as age, gender etc	Could
1.4	Registration with social login	Should
1.5	Different roles and access for citizens and cities	Must
1.6	Like stories	Should
1.7	Report stories	Should
1.8	Report comments	Could
1.9	Create tags	Won't
1.10	Delete their stories	Must
1.11	Limit on number of comments under a story	Could
1.12	Limit on number of comments in a given timeframe	Could
1.13	Follow a story	Won't
1.14	Delete their account along with all associated data	Must
2	Stories	
2.1	Template for creating new stories	Must
2.2	Story creation only for authenticated users	Must
2.3	Story text length limit	Should
2.4	Stories contain text	Must
2.5	Stories contain image	Must
2.6	Stories contain video	Should
2.7	Stories contain audio	Could

2.8	Stories contain combinations of formats like text over image	Must
2.9	Image gallery for stories	Should
2.10	Text prompts for stories	Could
2.11	Stories must have geographic information	Must
2.12	Comments	Could
2.13	Comment length limit	Could
2.14	Share to social media	Should
2.15	Stories must be displayed on a map	Must
2.16	Stories must be displayed on a timeline	Must
2.17	Stories have tags	Should
2.18	Predefined list with tags	Should
2.19	Filtered search of stories	Should
2.20	Limit on story pages	Should
2.21	Scrollytelling format	Must
2.22	Creator username should not be visible in the story	Won't
2.23	Automatic creation of subtitles for the audio/video files that stories may have	Won't
2.24	Cities should approve each story before publishing it	Should
2.25	Cities should be able to disable comments	Could
2.26	Automatic translation of the stories content	Won't
2.27	Stories contain maps	Must
2.28	Stories contain before-after image comparison module	Should
2.29	Navigation to next story from the story view page	Should
2.30	Ability to add text on images to provide credit or information	Could
2.31	Ability to format text and add hyperlinks	Must
2.32	Map comparison module	Could
2.34	Desktop and mobile preview of story during creation	Could

3	Threads	
3.1	Cities can create Threads	Must
3.2	Thumbnail for the preview	Should
3.3	Threads should have tags	Should
3.4	Limit of stories under a thread	Won't
3.5	Connection of threads with resources	Could
3.6	Thread end date	Could
4	Resources	
4.1	Cities can create resources	Should
4.2	Different resources categories	Could
4.3	Support all media types available for stories	Could
5	Home page	
5.1	Home page with scrollytelling format	Must
5.2	Template for creating and editing the home page	Must
5.3	Page numbering	Could
5.4	Connection with stories	Should
6	General	
6.1	It should be inclusive	Should
6.2	Customized settings per city (disable/enable features)	Must
6.3	Available in the languages of the different cities (not the user-generated content)	Must
6.4	See stories from other cities	Could
6.5	Mobile friendly	Should
6.6	Analytics about the stories	Could
6.7	The tool should be available for a city	Must
6.8	The tool should be available for a neighborhood	Could
6.9	The content must be available without registration	Must

6.10	Forum	Won't
6.11	Different basemaps for the map	Could
6.12	Cities can add extra layers on the map	Should
6.13	Story pins on map open the story preview when clicked	Should
6.14	Draft saving for content	Should
6.15	Notifications	Should
6.16	City council logo next to each city name	Could
6.17	Draw custom layers on the map	Should
6.18	Add ArcGIS layer on the map	Should
6.20	Dark theme	Could

Annex 2: Informed Consent Form

Neutrality Story Maps Workshop Consent Form

Start of Block: Informed Consent

Introduction You have been invited to participate in a workshop under the framework of the European project Urban Planning and design ready for 2030 (UP2030). UP2030 aims to guide cities through the socio-technical transitions required to meet their climate neutrality ambitions. Imec-SMIT, Vrije Universiteit Brussel (VUB) and CErTH's role in the project is to develop, test and validate citizen engagement state-of-the-art methods and digital tools, to support better decision-making on spatial solutions. With your participation you will make a substantial contribution to the development of the Neutrality Story Maps tool, which are map-based stories by citizens on the topic of climate change and climate transitions in the city. Based on the concepts of digital storytelling, Neutrality Story Maps allow the sharing of experiences, issues, concerns, hopes and needs regarding climate and sustainability in the city through a narrative format. The workshop is set to take 1 hour and 45 minutes and will include testing the platform and providing feedback on positive aspects and areas for improvement.

Please provide the information requested below. It will be used solely for research purposes and will help us better tailor the tool to suit users with your background.

- Age (1) _____
- Gender (2) _____
- Nationality (3) _____
- Field of Study (4) _____
- Education Level (5) _____

I have been provided with information about the task and my rights as a participant.

In relation to this task:

I agree to take part in this workshop as a participant and complete all the exercises that aim to understand the end users' needs and objectives, which will be linked to the development of the Neutrality Story Maps tool.

I agree that my personal data which is gathered during and as the result of my participation in this task will be (i) collected and retained for the purpose of this project, (ii) accessed and analyzed by the imec-SMIT VUB researchers for the purpose of improving the Neutrality Story Maps tool.

I agree that the analysis of the insights gathered in this workshop might be used for academic publications.

I acknowledge that:

My participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw from participation at any time without explanation.

My anonymity is guaranteed, and I will not be identified in publications or otherwise without my express written consent.

I am aware of the legal ground on which the processing of my personal data is based, namely consent as per Art. 6 (1) (a) GDPR.

I am aware that I might withdraw my consent for the processing of my personal data, however without affecting the lawfulness of the processing prior to the withdrawal of consent.

I am aware that I have the following rights as a data subject, which I can exercise with the controller:

The right to access.

The right to rectification.

The right to erasure.

The right to restriction of processing.

The right to be informed about recipients after a request for rectification, erasure or restriction of processing.

The right to data portability.

The right to object.

The right not to be subjected to automated individual decision-making, including profiling.

To file a complaint to my national Data Protection Authority.

I am aware that the controller and processor of my personal data provided in the context of this participation is VUB (Vrije Universiteit Brussel), Pleinlaan 2, 1050 Brussels, company number 449.012.406.

If you have questions or if you wish to exercise your rights, you can contact Milutin Djuraskovic (milutin.djuraskovic@vub.be) or the data protection officer of VUB (dpo@vub.be).

I am aware that the recipients or categories of recipients of the personal data are VUB.

I have been informed of the procedure on how to exercise these rights with the controller, namely: sending an e-mail to milutin.djuraskovic@vub.be or the data protection officer of VUB (dpo@vub.be).

I am aware of the purposes for which my data is gathered and processed in this project, namely: collecting user requirements based on which the Neutrality Story Maps platform will be improved.

My data will be protected and kept safe throughout this project and accessed and analysed by imec-SMIT, Vrije Universiteit Brussel researchers for the purpose of implementing this project.

My data will be stored for the duration of the project and kept for 5 years after the final payment of Grant Agreement 101096405.

By signing this document, I agree to:

Participate in this workshop under the terms set out above

The processing of my personal data

- I consent, begin the study (1)
- I do not consent, I do not wish to participate (2)